

HARVARD COLLEGE

SENIOR THESIS

**Life's First Steps: Exploring the
Feasibility of Prebiotic Chemical
Reactions Through Ultraviolet
Dependence**

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*A thesis presented to the Department of Astronomy
in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Bachelor of Arts in Chemistry and Astrophysics*

under the

Faculty of Arts and Sciences

Submitted on the 11th of April, 2015

*"Imagination will often carry us to worlds that never were.
But without it we go nowhere."*

Carl Sagan in *Cosmos* (1980, p.4)

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Abstract

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by Christopher J. MAGNANI

Beginning with the Miller-Urey Experiments¹, the laboratory has been essential in exploring the chemical origins of life. In the last decade, plausible prebiotic syntheses have been proposed for RNA² and its simple sugar building blocks³. Many chemical pathways leading to biological precursor molecules invoke ultraviolet energy as a driving force²⁻⁷, but most studies refrain from delving deeply into the light-activated mechanisms, preferring to focus on the chemistry's synthetic possibilities. Because traditional laboratory methods of simulating the primordial UV environment do not accurately reflect the prebiotic Earth and UV activity is generally wavelength dependent⁸, it is essential to develop methods to evaluate the feasibility of key prebiotic photochemical processes by probing their wavelength dependence. This thesis proposes a new method for characterizing the UV sensitivity of reactions, enabling construction of quantum yield curves that provide the wavelength dependence of prebiotic photochemical processes, which can provide insight into the type of photochemical mechanism driving a reaction. By coupling quantum yield curves with astrophysical models detailing the surface UV environment⁹⁻¹³, it becomes possible to evaluate reaction feasibility under conditions found on the prebiotic Earth or even exoplanet systems, allowing for the development of constraints to narrow the search for life elsewhere in the galaxy.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my advisor, Professor Dimitar D. Sassellov, for all of his guidance, support, and patience throughout my undergraduate career and particularly over the course of this project. Dimitar cultivates an infectious aura of excitement that encourages his students to ponder the big questions of our time and leap into the unexpected. Dimitar not only made it possible for me to work on a project so perfectly tailored to my interests, situated in the interdisciplinary space between chemistry and astrophysics, but also encouraged me to take the risk to explore a field still in its infancy in order to pursue the most exciting questions about life's beginnings.

I would also like to thank Professor Jack W. Szostak for his willingness to collaborate with our team and for allowing me to use his facility in the Center for Computational and Integrative Biology at Massachusetts General Hospital. Use of his facility and equipment enabled me to explore the chemistry at the heart of my questions which would not otherwise have been possible.

I would like to thank Professor Charles R. Alcock for his oversight of the senior thesis program and his assistance in helping me turn my ambitions into the completed document you see today.

Sukrit Ranjan, along with Dimitar, provided the original motivation for exploring ultraviolet-dependent prebiotic chemistry, and he was an integral sounding board as I designed the experimental framework of the project. Sukrit oriented me within the larger context of the questions being explored by the Sassellov Group, and I am extremely grateful for all of Sukrit's advice and especially his willingness to take the time to help me even when my questions were naïve.

I want to thank Dr. Albert Fahrenbach for all of his help on the chemistry side of the project, particularly with the chemical procedures. His help was indispensable as I navigated the world of organic synthesis, and his sense of humor made long

days in the lab considerably shorter.

I would like to thank Dr. Anders Björkbom for all of his help with the LC-MS and his role in identifying the LC-MS conditions ideal for the oxazolidinone. I also want to thank Anders for his jokes and stories that made time in the lab much more fun.

I want to thank Dr. Alexei Trifonov and Dr. Alex Glenday for their help with the UV equipment and their efforts to ensure that the tunable lamp was properly assembled and aligned.

I want to thank Jamie Villanueva for his boundless energy in answering all of my emails and facilitating my involvement with the Origins of Life Initiative. I can always count on Jamie's warm smile whenever I see him.

I want to thank the Origins of Life Initiative for supplying the majority of this project's funding and for the support of the grants they awarded me. I would also like to thank the Harvard College Program for Research in Science and Engineering (PRISE) for funding and supporting my efforts.

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Abbreviations

ACN	Acetonitrile
NH₃	Ammonia
D₂O	Deuterium Oxide
HCN	Hydrogen Cyanide
Hg	Mercury
IR	Infrared
KCN	Potassium Cyanide
KNCO	Potassium Cyanate
LC-MS	Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry
MS	Mass Spectrometry
MS-MS	Mass Spectrometry-Mass Spectrometry
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
PFP	Pentafluorophenyl
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
TEA	Triethylamine
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography
UV	Ultraviolet
Xe	Xenon

Chapter 1

Purpose

Traditionally, the origins of life have been explored in the chemical laboratory where there are inherent limits to approximating the conditions of the early Earth^{2-4,6,7}. In more recent times, the ongoing boom in exoplanet research—with 1,827 confirmed exoplanets as of 11 April 2015¹⁴—raises the question of chemical possibilities on these worlds and how to allocate observational resources for narrowing the search for life in the galaxy; consequently, it is of interest to develop methods better able to probe the relationship between life’s beginnings and the prebiotic environment.

The primary objective of this study is to connect the chemical laboratory to the constraints of planetary conditions by developing a method for systematic study of the ultraviolet dependence of key prebiotic photochemical reactions through the construction of quantum yield curves, which provide information about how effectively reactions proceed as a function of wavelength. Reactions with broad quantum yield curves demonstrating activity across many wavelengths can be considered robust and viable in a wide range of planetary environments, while reactions with narrow quantum yield curves demonstrating

dependence on only a handful of wavelengths can be considered sensitive and viable under only specific conditions where those wavelengths are not diminished by something like atmospheric absorbance. Because the UV-environment present on the early Earth or an exoplanet can be determined through astrophysical modeling⁹⁻¹³, reactions with quantum yield curves showing more wavelength sensitivity can be used to assess the viability of specific chemical pathways on the prebiotic Earth or to determine what planetary conditions are necessary requirements for biogenesis.

In our investigation, we aim to study UV-dependence in detail by using a tunable UV source to provide wavelength isolation, and we will focus our efforts on a reaction known to utilize a copper(I) cyanide complex to convert dilute cyanide solutions into oxazolidinones, the derivatives of simple sugars needed in the synthesis of RNA³. Our objective is to investigate the UV-dependence of the photochemical process, developing a method to examine reaction rates under wavelength isolation. Such a method will make it possible to determine whether a reaction is robust or vulnerable to variations in the ultraviolet environment, and the shape of the quantum yield curve can help determine whether the UV-chemical interaction proceeds through a mechanism involving either (i) generation of solvated electrons through photoionization³ or (ii) promotion of the copper complex into a specific excited state¹⁵.

Chapter 2

Introduction

We will begin our exploration of photochemical prebiotic reactions with an overview of the recent gains in the field as well as previous methods for simulating the prebiotic UV environment. This will set the stage for our interest in a more sophisticated technique utilizing quantum yield curves. We will then explore the chemistry used in our study to establish a background for our investigation of the reaction's ultraviolet mechanism.

2.1 Prebiotic Chemistry and the Primordial World

Laser-Raman imaging has detected the fossils of ancient microbes dating back to at least 3.5 Gyr¹⁶ and geochemical studies of the carbon isotopic record in sedimentary rocks suggests that life may have begun as early as 3.8 Gyr ago¹⁷, coinciding with the end of the heavy bombardment of the inner solar system¹⁸. The period before life, termed 'prebiotic,' was critical for supplying the environmental and chemical ingredients necessary for abiogenesis to occur. Impactors, like comets, were able to supply significant quantities of necessary

volatiles like water to the Earth's surface, with models based on the lunar impact record allowing for estimations of impact frequencies and delivered quantities¹⁹. Impactors as well as interplanetary dust particles would have provided organic feedstock molecules, including aromatics, nitrogen-containing heterocyclics, and amphiphilic compounds²⁰, expanding the availability of starting materials for prebiotic chemical syntheses by supplementing organics produced by geochemical²¹ or atmospheric processes²²⁻²⁴. Today, dust particles or meteorites small enough to be decelerated by the atmosphere continue to deliver these materials to Earth's surface¹⁸. Furthermore, materials present in ice on interstellar dust grains like amorphous H₂O, CO₂, CH₃OH, and NH₃ that enables such dust grains to act as sites for production of racemic glycine, alanine, serine, glycerol, ethanolamine, and glyceric acid, as reported in experiments simulating the interstellar environment²⁵.

The prebiotic atmosphere was also significant in the chemistry leading to life. The most significant difference from the present time is that the prebiotic world lacked oxygen and ozone, making the atmosphere a far less effective ultraviolet shield than it is today^{18,23}. Although it is now understood that conditions were less reducing than employed in the first pioneering studies²³ like the famous Miller-Urey experiments¹, it is understood that the prebiotic Earth had a weakly reducing atmosphere, composed of carbon dioxide, nitrogen, methane, and water vapor, which would have enabled productive synthesis through atmospheric reactions²³. Nevertheless, mildly reducing or even neutral atmospheres allow for atmospheric contributions to the prebiotic arsenal of available compounds²³, including the availability of methane, ammonia²⁶, and hydrogen cyanide²⁷. The impacts of extraterrestrial objects during the heavy bombardment and their interactions with the atmosphere would have allowed for 'shock-synthesis' of organic materials in the prebiotic atmosphere, supplying energy to reducing gas mixtures of methane, nitrogen, and water enabling synthesis of compounds like hydrocarbons, ammonia, cyanide, and amino acids¹⁸. Furthermore, UV flux, due to the

absence of oxygen, and lightning were also available energy sources for atmospheric reactions⁴.

Most interest in prebiotic chemistry has been directed at understanding chemical possibilities stemming from a variety of terrestrial environments, with the two most popular being shallow pools on the Earth's surface^{2,3} or hydrothermal vents beneath the ocean^{21,28}. In addition to thermally-activated pathways, hydrothermal vents also provide access to pH and redox gradients with potential to drive reactions⁴. Surface-based chemistry, however, benefits from access to multiple other energy sources, including ultraviolet energy from the Sun and electrical discharges from lightning, which enable access to photochemical and electrochemical pathways in addition to thermally-activated ones⁴. Astrophysical modelling informed by observational characterization allows prediction of UV surface environments by accounting for stellar output and absorbance by planetary atmospheres^{9,29,30}. Thus, astrophysical tools provide the opportunity to provide rigorous constraints on UV-dependent prebiotic chemistry. Consequently, explorations of UV-driven prebiotic chemistry have the potential to better match prebiotic simulations with actual conditions, thereby enhancing the relevance of discoveries in the laboratory.

Laboratory chemistry has been critical in the search for life's beginnings, allowing for the discovery of possible synthetic routes to key biological precursor molecules. At its birth in the 1950s, research into the chemical origins of life began when the Miller-Urey experiments demonstrated the production of amino acids in experiments using simulated lightning as an energy source¹. Around the same time, the biochemical role of nucleotides and their capacity for the storage and transfer of genetic information was revealed³¹⁻³⁴, which gave rise to the RNA World Hypothesis for the origins of life³⁵⁻³⁹. This hypothesis recognized that such information transfer is essential for life's beginning as it is integral to

initiating the process of Darwinian evolution that would have pushed biology to ever more complex molecular and cellular forms^{5,40}. Additionally, single-stranded RNA seems the likely precursor to modern biology's information molecule because it has the capacity for self-replication as well as the ability to exhibit enzymatic activity, opening the possibility for additional important roles in the dawn of biogenesis^{3,5,40}. Significant progress has been made that has substantially supported the RNA World. Recent work by the Sutherland group has demonstrated under plausible prebiotic conditions in the lab both a complete synthesis of RNA pyrimidines², and a copper cyanide complex capable of catalyzing the generation of the simple sugars needed as building blocks for RNA synthesis from dilute cyanide solutions³. In this work we investigate the later discovery, exploring in detail the photochemical process driving the conversion of cyanide into simple sugars.

FIGURE 2.1: The RNA World and Metabolism-First Hypotheses attempt to explain life's origins by essentially arranging in a different order the events believed to be necessary steps in the path to biogenesis⁴¹.

While the RNA World Hypothesis directs investigations of life's origins towards understanding natural pathways that could have produced RNA, other

investigators have taken a different ‘metabolism first’ approach (see Fig 2.1)^{41–43}. These studies seek to demonstrate the viability of reactions resembling those used in biology’s metabolic cycles in a prebiotic setting, which would supply energy rich molecules fueling the first synthetic reactions and possibly feeding the first cellular organisms^{41–43}. For example, it has been demonstrated that parts of the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle, the reverse of the Krebs Cycle, are viable under prebiotic conditions via an ultraviolet energy channel^{6,7}. While it is likely that both the genesis of RNA and simple metabolism were both essential to paving the way for life, our work will build off of a foundation set in the RNA World, exploring photochemical reactions employed in chemical pathways leading to the synthesis of RNA and its simple sugar building blocks^{2,3}.

2.2 The Primordial UV Environment

A distinctive feature of the prebiotic environment was the absence of oxygen, which is believed to have resulted in substantially greater ultraviolet fluxes reaching the Earth’s surface^{18,23}. Furthermore, through work observing solar analogs and modeling solar evolution^{11,13,18}, it is understood that the Sun had a greater luminosity at short ultraviolet wavelengths than it does today¹⁸. Figure 2.2 displays the larger ultraviolet energies delivered to the prebiotic Earth’s surface between 4.4 and 3.6 Gyr ago as compared to the present, especially below 230 nm¹⁸. By comparing the spectra of solar analogs representing the younger Sun, like κ -Ceti in Figure 2.3¹¹, with present-day solar output, it is possible to construct astrophysical models following solar output through time¹⁰. However, the lack of UV shielding by atmospheric oxygen had a more significant effect^{18,23}. It is also essential to consider the effect of UV absorption by water. Figure 2.4 displays the effect of water on the ultraviolet spectrum of the 3.9 Gyr old Sun,

which causes dramatic attenuation with only small quantities present (Ranjan & Sasselov in prep. 2015).

The sensitivity of the ultraviolet environment to environmental conditions, especially water content and atmospheric composition, makes it important to explore the UV dependence of key prebiotic photochemical reactions. Because UV energy can be used to either destroy molecules or to drive photochemical steps in synthetic pathways and such processes generally exhibit wavelength dependence⁸, variations in UV conditions could have significant repercussions for prebiotic synthesis, as different environments could select for different photochemical processes. This study aims to make it possible to determine a reaction's UV dependence and thereby enable evaluation of reaction viability under UV conditions specified by the environmental factors present on either the primordial Earth or on exoplanets.

2.3 Tradiational Laboratory UV Simulations

Most experimental work in prebiotic chemistry employing ultraviolet light as an energy source has not attempted to simulate the primordial UV environment in precise detail, as the focus is usually on the synthetic possibilities of the chemical environment rather than analyzing environmental constraints due to UV irradiation. Consequently, preference in laboratory simulations has historically been given to easily used UV lamps, often containing mercury or xenon gas, with the UV output characterized by line emission^{2-4,6,7}. These lamps deliver high fluxes at resonant emission lines and some continuum emission through the effects of pressure broadening^{8,44}, but these arc lamp spectra (e.g. Figs 3.1, 3.3, 3.5) clearly differ from that of the primordial sun shown in Figure 2.3. This mismatch between the UV arc lamps and the primordial environment is explored in Chapter

FIGURE 2.2: Solar output has experienced a wavelength-dependent evolution with time, with significant decreases in the low λ deep UV and increases at higher λ . Note the log scale on the y axis¹⁸.

3 and demonstrated by the difference in flux ratios displayed in Table 3.2. From an organic chemistry perspective, these lamps are viewed as energy sources providing the high energy photons needed for photochemical reactions; however, wavelength dependence is often weighted with less importance as long as the chemistry does proceed. However, because UV energy can both be used to form molecules as well as destroy bonds⁸, relative UV flux can have an impact on reaction rate, or even viability, for wavelength dependent processes. By paying attention to wavelength dependence, it becomes possible to assess whether the results of a simulation will hold under the actual primordial conditions.

Arc lamps are designed with two electrodes separated from one another in a gas-filled chamber^{8,44}. When voltage is applied, an electric arc forms between

FIGURE 2.3: The solar spectrum has not remained constant, instead evolving with time to become comparatively less luminous in the deep UV. Shown are the overlaid spectra of the modern Sun (red) and a solar analog, κ -Ceti, representing the prebiotic Sun (black). Note the log scale on the y axis¹¹.

the electrodes, resulting in excitation of the gas which then emits photons through fluorescence, with emitted photons having energies corresponding to the difference in the relaxed and excited energy levels of the gas^{8,44}. While the primary emission will occur at the transitions associated with the particular gas being used, pressure broadening allows for continuum emission^{8,44}.

Arc lamps employed in chemistry are typically used in a few different designs. The most commonly used is an external UV source, with a lamp housing containing the arc lamp projecting UV irradiation onto the reaction vessel (e.g. Figs 2.6 and 2.7), which has the advantage of allowing for manipulation of the irradiation using optical devices like filters. In our experiment we use a variant

FIGURE 2.4: The prebiotic UV spectrum becomes more attenuated as the quantity of water increases. Note the log scale on the y axis (Ranjan and Sasselov in prep. 2015).

of this set up employing a diffraction grating to isolate desired wavelengths (Fig 2.7). Another design is that of a photochemical reactor, consisting of a chamber surrounded by arc lamps within which a reaction vessel can be placed. While this only allows for minimal control of the UV environment by changing the lamps used, it allows for delivery of high UV fluxes in order to increase the rate of photochemical reactions (e.g. Fig 2.5). A different arc lamp design utilizes an immersion well to place the lamp inside the reaction vessel, as shown in Figure 2.8. This has the advantage of maximizing delivered UV flux, but, as with the photochemical reactor does not allow for much control of the UV wavelengths delivered beyond the type of lamp used. In Section 2.4 we will describe the UV sources used in this study.

2.4 Description of UV Arc Lamp Sources

2.4.1 Externally Irradiating Lamps

Most UV chemistry performed in the laboratory employs one of two arc lamp system designs. The most common design uses external irradiation, where the reaction flask is exposed to an external source. This category includes both photochemical reactors, such as the Rayonet RPR-200 (Fig 2.5) used in Ritson and Sutherland's 2012 experiment³, and external lamp housings that project irradiation onto a reaction flask, like the 150 W Newport Low-Pressure Hg(Xe) Lamp (Fig 2.6). Photochemical reactors allow for the delivery of high fluxes at the cost of wavelength control by surrounding the reaction flask with several lamps. In order to change the UV environment in a photochemical reactor, the lamps themselves must be changed. External lamp housings enable wavelength control by passing the emitted broadband spectrum through manipulative devices like filters before delivery to the reaction vessel; however, such manipulations have the cost of diminishing flux arriving at the sample. The 75 W Tunable PowerArc system (Fig 2.7) falls under the category of an external lamp housing, with manipulation of the delivered UV flux made possible by an attached monochromator (which separates the light with a diffraction grating allowing the slit position to determine the selected wavelength). Both the Rayonet Photochemical Reactor and the Tunable PowerArc are used in this study to explore the UV dependence of prebiotic photochemical reactions.

FIGURE 2.5: The Rayonet RPR-200 Photochemical Reactor is equipped with 16 lamps arranged around a central chamber where the reaction vessel is placed. The lamps used were optimized for the 254 nm mercury emission feature, which is responsible for >90 percent of emission. This is the UV system used by the Sutherland group in their 2012 study demonstrating the synthesis of simple sugars from dilute CN^{-3} .

FIGURE 2.6: The 150 W Newport Low-Pressure Hg(Xe) Lamp irradiates the reaction flask from an external lamp housing. It is possible to manipulate the delivered UV flux via the placement of optical devices such as filters in between the lamp and the reaction vessel.

FIGURE 2.7: The 75 W Tunable PowerArc manufactured by Optical building Blocks (OBB) couples a xenon arc lamp with a monochromator to enable precise wavelength selection. The monochromator is a diffraction grating that separates the lamp's spectrum by wavelength, allowing for wavelength selection based on the relative position of the grating and the exit slit. The system includes an enclosed compartment to house the cuvette, allowing for the entire system to be purged with N_2 gas.

2.4.2 Immersion Lamps

The second major UV arc lamp design is that of the immersion lamp. An immersion lamp is placed inside a reaction vessel, often using a quartz immersion sleeve, allowing for maximizing the available flux by surrounding the lamp on all sides with the reaction mixture. This design does not allow for significant wavelength control, but has the advantage that controlling atmospheric O_2 absorption of UV is easier, as only the quartz sleeve containing the lamp must be purged. An example of such an apparatus using a 450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp is displayed in Figure 2.8, which is the same device used in Guzman and Martin's 2008 experiment that demonstrated the viability of the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle under prebiotic conditions⁶.

FIGURE 2.8: The 450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp allows for immersion of the lamp inside a reaction vessel via a quartz sleeve. Pictured is the lamp positioned inside the sleeve and reaction vessel, as well as the location of the spectrometer when the lamp's spectrum was measured. This is the exact apparatus used in Guzman and Martin's 2008 experiment exploring the reductive tricarboxylic acid cycle under prebiotic conditions⁶.

2.5 Ritson & Sutherland's 2012 Sugar Synthesis

FIGURE 2.9: The two major products of The Ritson Process are oxazolidinone derivatives of glycolaldehyde and glyceraldehyde, **1** and **2**, respectively³.

The Sutherland group's studies demonstrate a plausible prebiotic synthesis of RNA² as well as a source for the simple sugars that they use as starting

materials³. Both of these syntheses involve UV driven steps, but for the purpose of this study we decided to focus on the generation of the sugar derivatives, as the chemistry is simpler, involving a single one-pot reaction, which simplifies the development of a method to empirically measure sensitivity of the reaction to UV. This reaction, which we will sometimes refer to as the Ritson Process, employs a tricyanocuprate(I) complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_3]^{2-}$, as a catalyst in the conversion of HCN into oxazolidinones **1** and **2** (Figure 2.9), derivatives of glycolaldehyde and glyceraldehyde, respectively³. The Sutherland group proposed that the syntheses of **1** and **2** displayed in Figure 2.11 are driven by a photoredox cycle involving the cyanocuprate(I) complex shown in Figure 2.10. Sutherland's mechanism proposes that the cyanocuprate(I) complex acts to generate solvated electrons which are then used to reduce the nitrile bond in HCN, initiating the synthesis of the oxazolidinones. In order to regenerate the catalyst, Sutherland invokes the photoredox cycle of tricyanocuprate(I) shown in Figure 2.10 generating cyanogen, $(\text{CN})_2$, and two protons per cycle³. This process being both a one-pot synthesis and entirely dependent on UV irradiation makes it an optimal probe for our study. Furthermore, given that cyanide, the only feedstock molecule for this reaction, is understood to be relatively common from an astrophysical perspective¹⁸⁻²⁰, and there are good arguments for its high abundance on the prebiotic Earth exists^{18-20,23,26,27,45}. It is conceivable that the dependence of this reaction on UV wavelengths and intensity available in a given planetary environment could serve as a preliminary indicator in support of RNA based life, as this reaction serves as a first step in the prebiotic manufacture of RNA.

FIGURE 2.10: Ritson and Sutherland proposed that tricyanocuprate(I) underwent a photoredox cycle under UV irradiation, supplying solvated electrons needed to reduce nitrile bonds in their proposed pathway for simple sugar synthesis (Fig 2.11). After UV photons strip the complex of electrons, the cycle regenerates the copper(I) cyanide catalyst while also producing protons and cyanogen³.

2.6 Banerjee's Alternative Mechanism

While Sutherland suggested the UV mechanism involved the generation of solvated electrons via a photoredox cycle (Fig 2.10)³, Banerjee *et al.* proposed a theoretical argument for an alternative process in which the tricyanocuprate(I) complex is instead advanced from a ground state, S_0 , to an excited state, S_1 , which can then convert to a reactive triplet, T_1 , via intersystem crossing¹⁵. If the UV-dependence of the reaction suggests a specific excitation, manifested by reaction activity occurring only within a narrow range of wavelengths, this could be tested and confirmed using time-resolved emission spectroscopy⁴⁶. Banerjee *et al.* also calculate a theoretical excitation wavelength of 265 nm for the excitation from S_0 to S_1 ¹⁵. This excitation allows the complex to associate with HCN directly, mediating an electron extraction followed by departure as a dipole-bound anion as shown in Figure 2.12. In their theoretical argument, Banerjee *et al.* are able

FIGURE 2.11: The Ritson Reaction converts dilute HCN into the major product **1** (boxed red). The proposed synthesis depends on the inorganic photoredox cycling of $[\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_3]^{2-}$ displayed in Figure 2.10, with the dependent steps boxed in blue. The final ring-forming step goes to completion, driving the reaction forward by Le Châtelier's Principle³.

to proceed through a proton coupled electron transfer (PCET) to the desired reduction of the nitrile bond in HCN, and the overall result of their mechanism is compatible with the remaining portion of Ritson and Sutherland's proposed pathway in Figure 2.11^{3,15}. However, in their theoretical argument, Banerjee *et al.* propose that HCN binds to the complex via nitrogen as indicated in Figure 2.12, which seems unlikely as such reactivity of HCN is unprecedented in the literature. Because this assumption is foundational to the theoretical argument proposed by Banerjee *et al.*, we must consider it with caution. However, even if the mechanism does not proceed exactly as proposed by Banerjee *et al.*, it is intriguing to consider an alternative UV mechanism for the results observed by Ritson and Sutherland based on excitation of the complex rather than production of solvated electrons.

FIGURE 2.12: The UV mechanism proposed by Banerjee *et al.* with the excitation event boxed in blue and curious associations of HCN via the nitrogen indicated with red arrows¹⁵.

2.7 Quantum Yield Curves

A quantum yield describes the progression of a reaction as governed by incident flux, in other words, the number of molecules reacting per number of incident photons. Quantum efficiency describes the efficiency of an absorbed photon in driving a process, or the number of molecules reacting per number of excited molecules^{8,47}. The absorption cross-section of the molecule, usually provided as an absorption spectrum, provides the number of molecules excited per number of incident photons; therefore, the absorption spectrum allows for interconversion between quantum yield and quantum efficiency⁸. These quantities are usually calculated for an entire experimental set-up, dividing the total production of products of a reaction (over a specific duration of time) by total incident photons without accounting for wavelength dependence of the light source⁸, which

can then be used to make comparisons between molecules or materials in standard environments, such as solar simulators for applications in energy technology⁴⁸ or cancer research where the susceptibility of biological molecules like DNA to UV damage is of interest⁴⁹. To calculate quantum yields, reaction progression can be measured as either an absolute reaction yield and absolute quantity of delivered photons over a specific length of time or the reaction rate and rate of delivered photons (flux) while maintaining a dependence on time^{8,49}. Our aim in this study is to develop a method to construct a wavelength-dependent quantum yield curve, using a strategy employing a tunable UV source to enable wavelength isolation and thereby obtain quantum yields for individual wavelengths which provide points on the quantum yield curve⁴⁷. This strategy will employ measurements of reaction rates and incident photon fluxes, maintaining time-dependence. When combined with the absorption spectrum for the copper(I) cyanide complex, this information will provide access to both quantum yield and quantum efficiency as a function of wavelength.

Chapter 3

Evaluating Traditional UV Arc Lamp Simulations

The first step in our investigation is to examine the standard methods currently used in the chemical laboratory to simulate the prebiotic UV environment. There are two major classes of lamp design for conducting UV chemistry. The first and most common is external irradiation, where the lamps irradiate a reaction from outside the reaction flask. This category includes photochemical reactors, like the Rayonet RPR-200 (Fig 2.5), and external lamp housings designed to project irradiation onto the flask, like the 150 W Newport Low-Pressure Hg(Xe) Lamp (Fig 2.6). Photochemical reactors consist of several lamps arranged within a chamber around a centrally located flask, allowing for high flux delivery at the cost of controlling wavelength availability (available wavelength can only be altered by changing the lamps themselves). External lamp housings allow for more wavelength control, as a broadband spectrum can be first passed through filters and other optical devices to control the delivered wavelengths; however, this control comes at the cost of decreased incident photon flux. The 75 W Tunable PowerArc system

(Fig 2.7) used in this study belongs to the second class of designs, as UV irradiation passes from the external lamp housing through a diffraction grating (the monochromator) before reaching the reaction in the cuvette.

In this chapter, we examine the spectra of several lamp systems, which can be compared to the primordial Sun's spectrum shown in Figure 2.3. While the spectra will not precisely resemble the prebiotic solar spectrum, relative ratios of integrated flux within the UVA, UVB, and UVC bands might be similar. To assess this claim, the ratios of the integrate fluxes for these lamps collected from the UVA, UVB, and UVC bands are compared to ratios generated from literature values for the prebiotic Earth 3.5–3.9 Gyr ago of 40 Wm², 5 Wm², and 1 Wm², for UVA, UVB, and UVC, respectively⁶, shown in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. This assessment of the UV spectral distribution and flux ratios reveals that none of the lamp systems resemble the prebiotic UV environment; however, while no system matches the ratios generated from literature values, the Tunable PowerArc used in this study comes closer than the other systems to doing so (Table 3.2).

The disconnect between prebiotic UV simulation in the lab and the actual primordial conditions is a point of concern, as without a proper match between prebiotic conditions and laboratory simulation it becomes uncertain whether laboratory findings are valid under actual conditions. Hence, it is important to develop new methods for probing the UV environment in a more systematic approach. The Tunable PowerArc enables such an investigation because wavelengths can be isolated via the monochromator, allowing for isolation of the wavelength dependence of photochemical reactions, as explored in the rest of this study.

3.1 Methods

First the spectra of the lamps were obtained. The monochromator for the 75 W Tunable PowerArc Xe Lamp was set to 0th order, effectively making the diffraction grating a mirror and allowing for passage of the complete spectrum. The spectrum was then obtained using an OceanOptics Spectrometer in ambient air under room temperature conditions. Spectra for the 150 W Newport Low-Pressure Hg(Xe) Lamp and 450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp were obtained with an OceanOptics USB2000 in ambient air under room temperature conditions using the experimental configurations displayed in Figures 2.6 and 2.8, respectively⁵⁰. Spectra were then processed using iPython Notebook to obtain plots of the full spectra (Figs 3.1, 3.3, and 3.5) as well as the portions in the UV (Figs 3.2, 3.4, and 3.6).

Integrated counts for the UVA, UVB, and UVC bands were then calculated for each spectrum using iPython Notebook (Table 3.1), where 200–280 nm was used to define UVC, 280–315 nm for UVB, and 315–400 nm for UVA. Integrated flux ratios were then calculated for UVA/UVB, UVA/UVC, and UVB/UVC (Table 3.2). Integrated flux ratios were also calculated using reported literature values of 40 Wm², 5 Wm², and 1 Wm², for UVA, UVB, and UVC, respectively (Table 3.2), representing the Earth 3.9–3.5 Gyr ago⁶.

3.2 Data

Included is a complete spectrum of the Tunable PowerArc (Fig 3.1) in counts per nm, and a zoomed in spectrum of the UV portion (Fig 3.2) is included for easier viewing. Likewise, full spectra of a 150 W Newport Low-Pressure Hg(Xe) (Fig 3.3) Lamp and a 450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp

(Fig 3.5) are supplied for comparison, and as for the Tunable PowerArc, zoomed in UV spectra are included for easier viewing (Fig 3.4 and Fig 3.6, respectively). The 150 W Newport Lamp (apparatus shown in Fig 2.6) represents a standard system designed for externally irradiating a reaction flask, while the 450 W Ace Glass Immersion Lamp (apparatus shown in Fig 2.8) is a standard example of a system designed to irradiate from within a reaction flask. The Newport and Ace Glass Lamps are included to allow for comparison of the Tunable PowerArc with lamp systems typically used for prebiotic UV simulation in the chemical laboratory.

TABLE 3.1: **Integrated UV Band Fluxes for Various Arc Lamps**

	UVC 200–280 nm	UVB 280–315 nm	UVA 315–400 nm
Literature ⁶ (W/m ²)	1	5	40
75 W Tunable PowerArc Xe Lamp (counts)	11,669.66	58,489.41	754,260.35
150 W Newport Hg(Xe) Lamp (counts)	6,813.01	15,327.66	112,321.80
450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp (counts)	2,106.88	1,002.05	1,754.66

TABLE 3.2: **UV Band Flux Ratios for Various Arc Lamps**

	UVA/UVB	UVA/UVC	UVB/UVC
Literature ⁶	8	40	5
75 W Tunable PowerArc Xe Lamp	12.896	64.634	5.012
150 W Newport Hg(Xe) Lamp	7.328	16.486	2.250
450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp	1.751	0.833	0.476

FIGURE 3.1: The 75 W Tunable PowerArc Xe Lamp delivers continuum emission across the UV, visible, and IR. Equipped with a monochromator, the Tunable PowerArc can isolate specific wavelengths and bands.

FIGURE 3.2: By zooming in on the UV portion of the spectrum in Figure 3.1, it is apparent that continuum emission extends into the UV; however, flux diminishes significantly as we approach shorter wavelengths.

FIGURE 3.3: The 150 W Newport Low-Pressure Hg(Xe) Lamp delivers continuum emission across the UV, visible, and IR much like the Tunable PowerArc (Fig 3.1); however, this system is only equipped with bandpass filters.

FIGURE 3.4: By zooming in on the UV portion of the spectrum in Figure 3.3, it is apparent that continuum emission extends into the UV; however, flux diminishes significantly as we approach shorter wavelengths.

FIGURE 3.5: The 450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp delivers flux primarily at the mercury emission lines, with the UV region dominated by the 254 nm line. There is also some continuum emission present in the visible portion of the spectrum. This exact lamp was used in Guzman and Martin's 2008 experiment⁶.

FIGURE 3.6: By zooming in on the UV portion of the spectrum in Figure 3.5, it is easier to see that the 254 nm mercury line dominates the UV spectrum. Additionally, continuum emission is absent.

3.3 Analysis and Discussion

From the processed spectra it is apparent that the lamp output (Figs 3.2, 3.4, and 3.6) differs significantly from the prebiotic solar spectrum (Fig 2.3). The solar spectrum in Figure 2.3 is defined by a continuum with emission features, such as the Lyman α line. The Tunable PowerArc (Fig 3.2) and the 150 W Newport Hg(Xe) (Fig 3.4) Lamps exhibit continuum emission but lack emission features like Lyman α in the UV, while the 450 W Ace Glass Lamp (Fig 3.6) lacks continuum emission in the UV while supplying Hg emission features markedly different from anything present in the Sun.

The lamps were also examined to see if they could serve as crude solar approximations by comparing the integrated flux ratios of the UVA, UVB, and UVC bands with those obtained from the literature⁶. Calculated ratios can then be compared individually with the literature (e.g. comparing the literature's UVA/UVB ratio with that of one of the lamps), or their relative sizes within a given simulation can be compared (e.g. comparing the relative size of the literature's UVA/UVB and UVA/UVC ratios with that of one of the lamps). The ratios of integrated fluxes differed markedly for all of the lamps with none of the simulations replicating the ratios obtained from the literature (Table 3.2). The 450 W Ace Glass Hg Immersion Lamp has ratios nowhere near that reported in the literature. While the Tunable PowerArc and Newport Lamps have ratios approaching closer to the literature, likely due to the continuum observed in their spectrum better reflecting the prebiotic Sun, they still differ substantially. The ratios closest to the literature prove to be for the Tunable PowerArc's UVB/UVC value of 5.012 and the Newport Lamp's UVA/UVB of 7.328, as compared to literature derived ratios of 5 and 8, respectively. Of all the systems tested, the Tunable PowerArc, although still different from the literature, comes closest to matching

all three ratios in Table 3.2, being the only system producing a UVA/UVB ratio being approximately $\frac{1}{5}$ that of the UVA/UVC ratio.

This analysis demonstrates that traditional laboratory methods of simulating the prebiotic UV environment with arc lamps are not accurate. While such methods can be more cost effective and easier to use, they will only produce viable results in situations where photochemical reactions have wavelength dependence consistent with the lamp's output. For reactions with substantial wavelength-dependence, it will be critical to more thoroughly probe their UV mechanisms in order to verify that such chemical activity is viable under actual prebiotic UV conditions, not just in the laboratory. While the Tunable PowerArc, like the other arc lamps, does not completely capture the nuances in the primordial solar spectrum, it has been equipped with a monochromator, allowing wavelength isolation. By isolating particular wavelengths, it is possible to probe wavelength dependence of reactions, from which reaction sensitivity to UV conditions can be understood. Essentially, wavelength isolation via the monochromator is able to overcome the Tunable PowerArc's shortcomings in precisely replicating a prebiotic solar spectrum.

Chapter 4

Revisiting Ritson and Sutherland's 2012 Experiment

In order to explore the UV mechanism present in the Ritson Process, it is necessary to first replicate and confirm their original results. By using the same kind of photoreactor, a Rayonet RPR-200 (Fig 2.5), equipped with Hg arc lamps optimized for the 254 nm emission line, conditions from the original experiment could be reproduced and applied to the reaction displayed in Figure 4.1. Oxazolidinone **1** was also obtained via an alternative synthesis (Fig 6.1) in order for $^1\text{H-NMR}$ comparison with the crude mixture produced by the UV reaction. After successfully detecting the desired product, oxazolidinone **1**, by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and LC-MS, a $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ analysis was performed, using ^{13}C enriched cyanide, reproducing the product peaks demonstrated by Sutherland's group (Fig 4.3)³. Taken together, these results confirm that the Ritson Process produces **1** when using the Rayonet photochemical reactor, and with Sutherland's results confirmed, the project was ready to move forward with developing a detection method (Chapter 6) to monitor changes in the reaction rate under different UV conditions.

4.1 Methods

FIGURE 4.1: Generalized reaction scheme for The Ritson Process³. For this study, the investigation is simplified by directing analytics solely towards product **1** as it is the major product, with Ritson and Sutherland reporting a 15% yield in their investigation³.

4.1.1 Oxazolidinone Detection with ¹H-NMR and LC-MS

The general procedure was adapted from Ritson and Sutherland's 2012 experiment³. First, 30 mg (0.461 mmol) KCN was dissolved in 2.2 mL H₂O in a 25 mL round-bottom flask. The solution was degassed with N₂ for approximately 20 minutes. While monitoring with an electronic Orion pH Meter (PerpHecT ROSS Comb. Micro pH, model number 8220BNWP), the pH was adjusted using 1 M HCl until it stabilized between 7.2 and 7.4. Then, 2 mg (0.022 mmol) CuCN was added, and the solution was again degassed with N₂ for 20 minutes. The solution was then transferred to a 10 mm wide 3 mL quartz cuvette with a 10 mm path length manufactured by Starna Cells. The cuvette was placed in the center of the chamber of a Rayonet RPR-200 Photochemical Reactor (Fig 2.5) with stirring and irradiated overnight for 17.5 hours using mercury lamps optimized for the 254 nm emission line. Within an hour, a brown precipitate was observed, which continued to accumulate over the course of the reaction. After irradiation, the crude reaction mixture was transferred to a 100 mL round-bottom flask and concentrated *in vacuo* (meaning solvent was evaporated by applying vacuum), resulting in a white and

brown solid. This material was dissolved in 1 mL D₂O and ¹H-NMR was taken (Fig 4.2). A sample from a 5 hour time-point was run through the LC-MS under acidic conditions on a Hilic column with 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid in water-ACN using an isocratic method with 90% ACN, using the method for sample preparation detailed in Chapter 6.

4.1.2 Obtaining Standard for ¹H-NMR Comparison with the Crude Mixture

To obtain a standard for ¹H-NMR comparison with the crude reaction mixture, **1** was synthesized using an adapted procedure reacting glycolaldehyde with cyanate (Fig 6.1) derived from both Ritson and Sutherland's 2012 experiment and a 1991 paper by Kovács *et al.*^{3,51}. First, 250 mg (2.082 mmol) of glycolaldehyde dimer was dissolved in 20 mL of H₂O in a 100 mL round-bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar. 1.35 g (16.642 mmol) of potassium cyanate was then added to the solution. The pH was monitored with an electronic Orion pH Meter (PerpHecT ROSS Comb. Micro pH, model number 8220BNWP) and maintained between 7 and 8 using 1 M HCl with approximately a total of 5.5 mL being added, with pH stabilizing over the course of an hour. The solution was then washed four times with 20 mL chloroform. The solution was extracted six times with 20 mL of a 4:1 ratio of chloroform to isopropanol. The organic extracts were collected in a 250 mL round-bottom flask and were concentrated *in vacuo*, producing a transparent oil. 2 mL of D₂O was used to dissolve this oil, before a ¹H-NMR was taken (Fig 6.3).

4.1.3 Oxazolidinone Detection with ^{13}C -NMR

The general procedure was adapted from Ritson and Sutherland's 2012 experiment³. First, 8.8 mL of a solution of 10% D_2O in water was degassed for 20 minutes with argon in a 50 mL round-bottom flask. 6.6 mL of this solution was then used to dissolve 90 mg (1.36 mmol) of K^{13}CN and 6 mg (0.07 mmol) of Cu(I)CN in a 25 mL round-bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar. While monitoring with an electronic Orion pH Meter (PerpHecT ROSS Comb. Micro pH, model number 8220BNWP), the pH was adjusted to 7.4 using 1.2 mL of 1 M HCl and 0.05 mL of 1 M NaOH. 400 μL of this solution was then transferred to a quartz NMR tube (Norell: S-5-600-SQTZ-8), which was capped and sealed with Parafilm. The tube was then irradiated at 254 nm using a Rayonet RPR-200 photochemical reactor, and every 45 minutes a ^{13}C -NMR was taken. The ^{13}C -NMR measurements were obtained using 265 scans, lasting for approximately 10 minutes, and the NMR was cooled to 4°C to slow any reactivity while the measurement was taken. The reaction was allowed to run overnight and a final time-point was taken at an elapsed time of 19 hours and 50 minutes, which was used to generate the ^{13}C -NMR displayed in Figure 4.3.

4.2 Data

^1H -NMR was used to identify the presence of product in the crude reaction mixture (Fig 4.2) by comparison with data from a standard (Fig 6.3) obtained via an alternative synthesis (Fig 6.1). ^{13}C -NMR was also taken using a procedure employing ^{13}C enriched cyanide, which demonstrated peaks associated with products **1** and **2** (Fig 4.3), as demonstrated in Ritson and Sutherland's original study³. With a sample of the crude mixture taken at the 5 hour mark, LC-MS was also

used for verification of product production by the Ritson Process using the the Rayonet photochemical reactor, employing the methodology detailed in Chapter 6. A mass of 104.0042 amu, reflecting M+H in the positive mode with retention time of approximately 3.5 minutes, matching both the mass and retention time obtained using the product standard (See Chapter 6).

FIGURE 4.2: This ¹H-NMR confirms the production of product **1** by the Ritson Process (Fig 4.1)³. After replicating the original experiment³, 2 of the 3 defining peaks of oxazolidinone **1** are clearly visible and delineated with red arrows. The third peak, normally present at 4.6 ppm is concealed within the strong water signal at 4.8 ppm. Notably, this NMR is noisy due to low product concentration.

FIGURE 4.3: By comparing the ^{13}C -NMR obtained using the Sutherland parameters (red) with that from the original experiment (black)³, it is clear that peaks associated with product **1** are present, indicating that the Ritson Process proceeds when using the Rayonet photochemical reactor.

4.3 Analysis and Discussion

In the original experiment, Ritson and Sutherland had used a comparison of the crude reaction mixture's ^1H -NMR as well as ^{13}C -NMR with that of purified standards in order to verify the identify of the UV reactions products (oxazolidinones **1** and **2**). As higher yield facilitates quantification and detection, it was decided for this study to focus solely on the major product, **1**, because Ritson and Sutherland reported a yield of 15% for **1** compared to 1-5% yield for **2**³. Here, their results have been replicated, as shown by the product peaks present

in the crude mixture's ^{13}C -NMR (Fig 4.3, which includes a comparison with the Sutherland group's results³) and ^1H -NMR (Fig 4.2, which can be compared to the ^1H -NMR of the standard, Fig 6.3). Furthermore, LC-MS analysis confirmed the presence of **1** in the crude mixture, detecting a mass of 104 amu in positive mode with a retention time of 3.5 minutes, matching the mass and retention time of the purified standard (Chapter 6). Although the ^1H -NMR only exhibited 2 of the 3 features identifying **1**, due to high noise and a strong water peak masking the third feature, when taken in combination with the ^{13}C -NMR and LC-MS data it is clear that the Ritson Process is successfully producing **1**. Now that the original experiment has been replicated, it is reasonable to continue to this project's next steps and analyze the cyanocuprate reaction's UV dependence.

Chapter 5

Absorption Spectrum of Tricyanocuprate(I)

After confirming the production of product **1** by the photochemical process described in Ritson and Sutherland's 2012 paper³ in Chapter 4, the next step in pursuing the UV dependence is to obtain an absorption spectrum. The absorption spectrum provides valuable information because in order for UV energy to be used to drive chemical reactions, it must first be absorbed⁸. Therefore, one would expect observed photochemical activity to increase at wavelengths coinciding with higher absorption. However, the absorption spectrum is not a direct probe for the UV-dependence of the reaction, as not all absorbed photons will be utilized in the desired photochemical process. Some photon absorptions will result in thermal conversion or re-emission, and some photochemical transitions will occur without the necessary localization of all reactants needed for the reaction to proceed within the lifetime of the photoactivated species^{6-8,23}. Most importantly, because the reaction pathway involves multiple steps, to analyze activity of the complex in isolation is insufficient, as a later step may be impeded by a given wavelength.

Nevertheless, the absorption spectrum is useful for preliminary insight into the copper(I) cyanide complex's UV activity as well as generation of the quantum efficiency, which is obtained by dividing the quantum yield curve by the absorption spectrum.

5.1 Methods

To prepare the complex, a modified version of Ritson and Sutherland's procedure was used³, informed by previous work on the properties of photoactive species of cyanocuprates⁵². 40 mL of deionized H₂O was degassed with argon in a 100 mL round-bottom flask for 30 minutes. 10 mL of degassed H₂O was then used to dissolve 65.6 mg (1.007 mmol) of KCN in a 25 mL round-bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar. The pH was then adjusted to 7.5 using 1.2 mL of 1 M HCl, monitoring with an electronic Orion pH Meter (PerpHecT ROSS Comb. Micro pH, model number 8220BNWP), resulting in a final cyanide concentration of 89 mM. Using a UV-Vis spectrometer and a Starna quartz cuvette (10 mm wide and 10 mm pathlength), an absorption spectrum was taken of a blank consisting only of 2.5 mL of deionized water (Fig 5.1), which was used to perform background subtractions on the other absorption spectra to account for the absorption effects of water, the cuvette, and oxygen in the air. The UV-Vis spectrometer and quartz cuvette were then used to take an absorption spectrum of 2.5 mL of the 89 mM cyanide solution (Fig 5.2). A 0.2 mM stock solution of the copper(I) cyanide complex with 1.1 equivalents of cyanide was then made, and an absorption spectrum of 2.5 mL of this solution was taken using the UV-Vis spectrometer and quartz cuvette (Fig 5.3). Additional spectra were taken of the complex as 0.1 equivalents of cyanide were added (Fig 5.4). The same cuvette was used for all absorption experiment for consistency.

5.2 Data

The absorption spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_3]^{2-}$ was obtained using a UV-Vis spectrometer, and provides preliminary information about the UV activity of the metal complex. The tricyano species dominates the spectrum because the dicyano species is not photoactive⁵² and the tetracyano species is in insignificant concentration, not being thermodynamically favored at neutral pH⁵². In order to account for the effects of absorbance by oxygen and water, a background subtraction was performed using a blank taken with pure deionized water (Fig 5.1). The UV-Vis spectrometer returns the absorption in 'absorbance units,' which arise from the equation:

$$A = \log_{10}\left(\frac{I_o}{I}\right) \quad (5.1)$$

where I_o is the incident light intensity and I is the transmitted intensity⁵³.

FIGURE 5.1: Here absorption is given as a function of wavelength for deionized water, and it can be seen that absorption increases with shorter wavelength. This spectrum was used to perform background subtractions for the rest of the absorption spectra to account for the effects of water, the cuvette, and oxygen.

FIGURE 5.2: The absorption spectrum for 89 mM KCN demonstrates that absorption increases substantially at shorter wavelength. Peaks are absent above 200 nm and once 2.0 absorption units the detector became saturated.

FIGURE 5.3: The absorption spectrum of 0.2 mM tricyanocuprate(I) exhibits λ_{max} peaks at 233 nm and 209 nm, with a minor peak at 223 nm; additionally, absorption is observed up to 300 nm, including Hg's 254 nm emission line.

FIGURE 5.4: The absorption spectra of the 0.2 mM tricyanocuprate(I) solution demonstrate that with increasing cyanide concentration, cyanide absorption (isolated in Fig 5.2) becomes increasingly strong, making it harder to identify the copper complex's peaks near 233 nm, 223 nm, and 209 nm. Additionally, the peak starting at 233 nm shifts to higher wavelength with increased cyanide concentration, indicating that more of the tricyanocuprate(I) species is present relative to the dicyano species⁵².

5.3 Analysis and Discussion

The absorption spectrum provides valuable information, as absorption is first required in order to use UV energy to drive chemistry⁸; therefore, absorption must occur at a given wavelength in order for the complex to exhibit photochemical activity. Absorption for the copper complex is dominated by the tricyanocuprate(I) species due to unfavorable thermodynamics for the tetracyano species at neutral pH and the photoinactivity of the dicyano species⁵². The absorption spectrum for 0.2 mM $[\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_3]^{2-}$ demonstrates that the complex exhibits absorption up to 300 nm (Fig 5.2), which includes the 254 nm Hg emission line

produced by Hg lamps used in previous laboratory experiments³ and the 265 nm excitation predicted by Banerjee *et al.*¹⁵; therefore the absorption spectrum rules out neither the photoredox cycle³ nor the 265 nm excitation¹⁵ hypotheses of the UV mechanism.

The absorption spectrum of the 0.2 mM copper(I) complex also exhibits several features of note, the λ_{max} peaks at 234 nm and 209 nm and the minor peak at 223 nm, which must be due to the copper complex as they are absent in the absorption spectrum of KCN (Fig 5.2). These features may correlate to properties of the complex that may have implications for the photochemical reaction, particularly if the UV mechanism depends on solvated electron production via photoredox cycling. In such a scenario, the ability of the complex to better absorb photons at a particular energy would presumably result in increased production of solvated electrons and reaction rate. However, the absorption spectrum cannot be directly substituted for the quantum yield curve's information about UV dependence, as not all absorbed photons will be utilized in the desired photochemical process. While the complex may better absorb at a given wavelength, it may not do so in such a way that productively directs the energy towards the desired photochemical process. For example, some photon absorptions will result in re-emission or conversion to thermal energy, and in order for the photochemical reaction to proceed, it is necessary for the reactants to come into contact during the lifetime of the photoactivated species^{6-8,23}. Furthermore, detailed analysis of the UV sensitivity of the entire reaction pathway (not just the isolated absorption by the copper(I) cyanide complex) is necessary, because there could be multiple UV-dependent steps later in the synthesis or UV-caused roadblocks, such as the degradation of intermediates. Nevertheless, the absorption spectrum encourages further investigation, as UV was absorbed throughout the region of interest.

The absorption spectrum will also allow conversion between the quantum yield curve and the quantum efficiency curve. The absorption spectrum provides the number of molecules excited per number of incident photons, the quantum efficiency curve provides number of molecules reacting per number of excited molecules, and the quantum yield curve provides the number of molecules reacting per number of incident photons^{8,47}. Therefore the quantum efficiency curve can be obtained by dividing the quantum yield curve by the absorption spectrum.

Chapter 6

Developing Analytics for UV Sensitivity Measurements

After verifying the production of **1** by the Ritson Process³ in Chapter 4 and demonstrating UV activity extending below 300 nm in the absorption spectrum of the the copper(I) cyanide complex (Fig 5.3), there were grounds for an in depth investigation of the UV mechanism driving the reaction. In order to study this reaction, it was necessary to develop analytical methods for determining the reaction rate and make quantitative comparisons between trials run under different ultraviolet conditions.

The first step of method development is to obtain a purified sample of product **1** of known concentration (Sections 6.1 and 6.4) to be used as a standard for determining the efficacy of the analytics and to calibrate our measurements. In this study, a LC-MS detection method was developed to allow for quantitative measurement of the concentration of product, enabling determination of reaction rates and making it possible to observe the effect of changes to the applied ultraviolet environment on reaction progression (Section 6.5).

To use LC-MS quantitatively, it was necessary to process samples uniformly, as inconsistent preparation between samples would mask the impact of changes to UV parameters on reaction rate. Consequently, an extraction method was developed using a glass 96-well plate in order to optimize uniformity (Section 6.6). Because product **1** is exposed to a variety of conditions over the course of processing and the LC-MS measurement, it was necessary to confirm product **1**'s stability under conditions such as acidity and freezing in order to ensure that degradation of **1** did not corrupt measurements.

After completing the development of an analytical method capable of quantitatively measuring the reaction rate, only determination of the incident photon flux (discussed in Chapter 7) remains before a quantum yield curve can be generated and the ultraviolet dependence of the chemical reactions be probed.

6.1 Alternative Synthesis of Oxazolidinone **1**

The first step in developing the analytics is to obtain a purified sample of product **1** to be used as a standard. The standard is necessary because it contains a known compound of known concentration that can be used to test detection methods and calibrate different techniques. Additionally, because in this case the standard is the same molecule produced by the studied reaction, product **1**, it can be used to understand the chemical properties of the molecule, such as its stability under conditions like freezing (Section 6.2) or acidity (Section 6.3) in addition to its ability to dissolve in different solutions. The standard's concentration can be calibrated using $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and co-axial Shegemi tubes (Section 6.4), allowing for a quantitative determination of the efficiency of sample preparation (Section 6.6) and generation of a LC-MS calibration curve, enabling conversion of relative LC-MS signals into quantified concentrations (Section 6.5).

6.1.1 Methods

FIGURE 6.1: Generalized reaction scheme for an alternative synthesis of oxazolidinone **1** by reacting glycolaldehyde with cyanate^{3,51}. Glycolaldehyde starting material is a dimer in solid form but dissociates in aqueous conditions⁵¹.

First, 20 mL of H₂O was degassed for 20 minutes with argon in a 100 mL round-bottom flask equipped with a stir bar. 250 mg (2.08 mmol) of glycolaldehyde dimer (note: in its solid state, glycolaldehyde exists as a dimer, but it dissociates under aqueous conditions⁵¹) and 1350 mg (16.64 mmol) of potassium cyanate were then dissolved in the degassed solution. The pH was monitored with an electronic Orion pH Meter (PerpHecT ROSS Comb. Micro pH, model number 8220BNWP) and maintained between 7 and 8 using 1 M HCl with approximately 4.5 mL being added in total. After stirring for approximately 30 minutes, the pH stabilized at 7.39, indicating that the reaction had gone to completion. The solution was washed six times with 20 mL of chloroform before it was extracted six times using a 4:1 ratio of chloroform to isopropanol. The organic extract was collected in a 250 mL round-bottom flask and concentrated *in vacuo*, producing a transparent oil. 2 mL of D₂O was used to dissolve the oil, and ¹H-NMR was taken (Fig 6.3). For comparison, ¹H-NMR of the starting material was obtained by dissolving 7 mg (0.058 mmol) of glycolaldehyde dimer in 1 mL D₂O (Fig 6.2).

Product **1** was found to be a poor candidate for analysis by TLC, showing no activity with most conventional stains and minimal activity under p-anisaldehyde (CAS: 123-11-5), with a preparation including 2.67 mL p-anisaldehyde, 3.33 mL sulfuric acid, 1.33 mL acetic acid, and 100 mL ethanol.

6.1.2 Data

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra were obtained for both the product **1** standard (Fig 6.3) and the glycolaldehyde starting material (Fig 6.2). The starting material exhibited a chaotic collection of peaks due to the numerous isomers associated with both glycolaldehyde and its dimer, which both exist in solution. These peaks are absent from the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of the purified sample of product **1** (Fig 6.3), which exhibited a clean spectrum save for some isopropanol impurity left over from the extraction. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (D_2O : δ 5.49 (1H, dd, J 6.1, 1.7), 4.57 (1H, dd, J 10.3, 6.1), 4.25 (1H, dd, J 10.3, 1.7)

FIGURE 6.2: This $^1\text{H-NMR}$ shows the features associated with the glycolaldehyde starting material. Because both glycolaldehyde and its dimers exist in solution and each has several isomers, a chaotic collection of peaks is observed. Notably, these peaks are absent in the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of the purified sample of product **1** shown in Figure 6.3

FIGURE 6.3: This ¹H-NMR shows the features associated with oxazolidinone **1**, as indicated by red arrows. The peaks indicated with blue arrows correspond to isopropanol, a remnant of the purification by extraction. Full evaporation of isopropanol was not pursued because product **1** proved most stable when left wet, as complete drying resulted in degradation. (Peaks corresponding to the starting material, shown in Figure 6.2, are absent.)

6.1.3 Analysis and Discussion

The synthesis of **1** by the reaction of cyanate with glycolaldehyde (Fig 6.1) followed by purification via organic extraction provided a clean sample as demonstrated by ¹H-NMR analysis (Fig 6.3) consistent with the literature³. Starting material peaks were absent in the final product, and the only impurity was isopropanol, a remnant of the extraction, which resulted from leaving the sample slightly wet after drying to preserve the stability of **1**. With this reliable method

for synthesising purified oxazolidinone **1** to be used as a standard, the project was ready to move forward with developing a method for preparing sample's for analysis.

6.2 Stability of Oxazolidinone When Frozen

The next key step was to verify the stability of product **1** when frozen. It is necessary to process all the samples for a time-course simultaneously because it is necessary to ensure that processing is applied uniformly to all samples and quantitation with LC-MS is most accurate when samples are analyzed together. Consequently, it is not possible to perform analysis in real time, and samples must be saved until all samples are ready for processing and the LC-MS is available to run analysis without interruption. If samples must be stored, it is advantageous to freeze them because this minimizes the risk of product degradation by hydrolysis that could occur at room temperature. However, because the end goal is to make quantitative comparisons, it is necessary to test the stability of product **1** when frozen in order to make sure that freezing does not introduce an additional variable, such as polymerization of the molecule. By confirming the stability of **1** under freezing conditions, it can be assured that freezing samples will not influence quantitation. By using $^1\text{H-NMR}$, it is possible to evaluate product stability, as reactivity in the form of degradation or polymerization will be evident from the introduction of new peaks in the NMR spectrum after freezing. After $^1\text{H-NMR}$ analysis, it was concluded that product **1** is indeed stable when frozen, as no new peaks were detected following freezing (Fig 6.4).

6.2.1 Methods

A 0.2 M solution of product **1** was prepared by reaction of glycolaldehyde with cyanate using the procedure outlined in Section 6.1 and calibration method outlined in Section 6.4. 2 mL of D₂O containing dissolved **1** was transferred to an oven-dried glass NMR tube of standard dimensions. A ¹H-NMR was taken (Fig 6.4a) before the NMR tube was sealed with Parafilm and placed in a -30 °C freezer overnight. The following day, the tube was removed and placed at room temperature to thaw before a ¹H-NMR of the sample was taken (Fig 6.4b).

6.2.2 Data

Using a calibrated 0.2 M solution of product **1** as a standard, ¹H-NMR spectra were obtained before and after freezing (Fig 6.4), with all three peaks of product **1** present in both spectra as well as some isopropanol impurity left over from the extraction implemented during purification. The post freezing sample differs only in that the water peak is more pronounced (larger and wider) with no new peaks arising, which can be attributed to weaker shimming of the NMR itself or to additional water entering the sample in the freezer (neither of which impact the stability of **1**). The absence of new peaks after freezing demonstrates that there is no effect on **1**'s stability.

6.2.3 Analysis and Discussion

Examining the ¹H-NMR spectra from before and after freezing (Figs 6.4a and 6.4b, respectively), it is clear that no degradation of **1** has occurred. Detection of new signal peaks would have indicated the presence of new molecules

FIGURE 6.4: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of 0.2 M oxazolidinone **1** before (a) and after (b) freezing. All three signature peaks of **1** (labelled with red arrows) can be observed in both spectra, and no new peaks arise after freezing, indicating that the product is stable. Both spectra exhibit some impurity attributable to isopropanol (labelled with blue arrows) remaining from the extraction used to purify **1**. The only difference is an enhanced water peak (larger and wider) at 4.8 ppm in (b), likely resulting from weaker shimming of the NMR instrument or from additional water entering the sample in the freezer, neither of which would have an impact on **1**'s stability.

arising from reactions such as hydrolysis or polymerization; however, no such detection was observed, indicating no such reactivity. The only noticeable difference observed in Figure 6.4 is that the water peak has become more prominent, being larger and wider. This is likely due increased contamination of the D₂O sample by H₂O entering the NMR tube while in the freezer or from weaker shimming of the NMR instrument itself; however, neither effect would impact the stability of **1**. After confirming that **1** can be frozen safely, the sample preparation method was free to take advantage of freezing samples.

6.3 Stability of Oxazolidinone Under Acidic Conditions

It is also necessary to verify that product **1** is stable under acidic conditions. The LC-MS method used to detect product uses acidic conditions on a Hilic column (Section 6.5). While the LC-MS method subjects product **1** to acidic conditions only over a short timescale, only a few minutes, it is still necessary to verify that the product is stable in order for acidic conditions to be used in a quantitative study, as acid can catalyze hydrolysis. After ¹H-NMR analysis of a sample at a pH of 8.5 and a pH of 0.5, it was concluded that product **1** is stable under acidic conditions, as no new peaks were detected following the change in pH (Fig 6.5), confirming that the LC-MS method developed in Section 6.5 can be used for quantitation.

6.3.1 Methods

A 0.2 M solution of product **1** was prepared by reaction of glycolaldehyde with cyanate using the procedure outlined in Section 6.1 and calibration method

outlined in Section 6.4. This sample was then diluted 100x with D₂O, resulting in a 2 mM solution of product **1**. 400 μL of this solution was transferred to an oven-dried glass NMR tube of standard dimensions, and a ¹H-NMR was taken (Fig 6.5a). The solution was then recovered from the NMR tube, and the pH was found to be 8.5 when measured with an electronic Orion pH Meter (PerpHecT ROSS Comb. Micro pH, model number 8220BNWP). 1 M DCl was then used to adjust the pH to 0.5, and the solution was allowed to sit for approximately an hour before a ¹H-NMR was taken of the acidic solution (Fig 6.5b).

6.3.2 Data

Using a calibrated 0.2 mM solution of product **1** as a standard, ¹H-NMR spectra were obtained before and after the pH was adjusted from 8.5 to 0.5 using 1 M DCl (Fig 6.5), with all three peaks of product **1** present in both spectra as well as some isopropanol impurity left over from the extraction implemented during purification. The spectra differ only in that pH slightly shifts the locations of signal peaks relative to water (an effect to be expected), but the absence of new signal peaks after the pH change demonstrates that there is no effect on **1**'s stability, as hydrolysis or other reactivity would manifest in the detection of new signals.

FIGURE 6.5: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of 2 mM oxazolidinone **1** before (a) and after (b) adjustment of pH from 8.5 to 0.5 using 1 M DCl. All three signature peaks of **1** (labelled with red arrows) can be observed in both spectra, as well as some impurity attributable to isopropanol (labelled with blue arrows) remaining from the purification of **1** by extraction. The only difference between spectra (a) and (b) is that pH slightly shifts the locations of signal peaks relative to water, which is an effect to be expected; however, because no new signal peaks are detected, it can be concluded that **1** is stable in acid.

6.3.3 Analysis and Discussion

Examining the ^1H -NMR spectra from before and after the pH adjustment from 8.5 to 0.5 (Figs 6.5a and 6.5b, respectively), it is clear that no degradation of **1** has occurred. Detection of new signal peaks would have indicated the presence of new molecules arising from reactions such as hydrolysis or polymerization; however, no such detection was observed, indicating no such reactivity. The only major difference observed in Figure 6.5 is that the locations of signal peaks relative to water shift slightly with the change in pH, which is an effect to be expected in NMR that has no bearing on the stability of product **1**. Because the absence of new signal peaks confirms that **1** is stable in acid, it is certainly reasonable to use a LC-MS detection method employing acidic conditions on a HILIC column (Section 6.5), especially since the product is only exposed to a low pH for a few minutes.

6.4 Calibrating the Standard's Concentration

Having a sample with a calibrated concentration holds numerous advantages for developing the analytical methods needed to quantitatively examine reaction rates. Firstly, a calibrated standard allows for conversion from relative signal intensities obtained from the LC-MS to quantified concentrations via a calibration curve generated from samples with known concentrations. Additionally, a calibrated standard allows determination of the efficiency of sample preparation (i.e. how much product is retained as the samples are processed).

The method used in this study to calibrate the standard's concentration uses NMR with Shegemis tubes equipped with coaxial inserts. Essentially this allows for NMR analysis of two solutions simultaneously, one with a known solution

to be used as a calibrator and the other being the sample of unknown concentration. This method has several advantages, the first being that a molecule's concentration in a crude mixture can be determined without contamination by the calibrating solution since the coaxial insert prevents the solutions from mixing, allowing for recovery of the product following the measurement. Furthermore, because the calculation depends only on the NMR signals of the molecules of interest while the signals of any contaminants can be ignored, it is possible to calibrate a crude solution, bypassing the difficulties associated with a rigorous purification.

The method developed for this project uses a known concentration of triethylamine (TEA) as the calibrating solution placed in the coaxial insert. First the conversion factor for TEA's signal intensity from inside the coaxial tube to the outer compartment must be determined, which was accomplished using a known concentrations of TEA and ethanolamine as the two solutions and comparing the normalized integrals of the peaks for NMRs taken with either TEA or ethanolamine in the coaxial insert. Having determined the conversion factor for TEA to be $X = 12.37$, it was then possible to use TEA as the calibrator, converting the signal intensity from inside the coaxial insert so that it could be compared to the signal of product **1**, which was in the solution in the outer compartment. The concentration of product **1** was then determined to be 0.2 M using the normalized integrals for the signals associated with the product and the calibrator.

6.4.1 Methods

The first step in calibrating the sample was determining the conversion factor, X , for the TEA calibrating solution's NMR signal from when the solution is inside the coaxial insert to the signal generated in the outer compartment of the Shegemi tube. This was accomplished using stock solutions of TEA

and ethanolamine in D₂O, each with 0.197 M concentrations, and Shegemi tubes equipped with coaxial inserts. 300 μL of each solution was used, with the first ¹H-NMR taken with ethanolamine inside the coaxial insert (Fig 6.6a) and the second taken with TEA inside the insert (Fig 6.6b). For each ¹H-NMR, the TEA peak at 1.0 ppm and the ethanolamine peak at 3.6 ppm were used for integration. The conversion factor from inside to outside was then calculated using Equation 6.1, where integrated NMR signals are referred to by labels with the molecule name and a subscript denoting location, either inside or outside the coaxial insert.

$$X = \sqrt{\frac{Ethanolamine_{out}}{TEA_{in}} \cdot \frac{TEA_{out}}{Ethanolamine_{in}}} = 12.37 \quad (6.1)$$

In order to calibrate the concentration of the purified product **1** for use as a standard, a calibrating ¹H-NMR was taken using a Shegemi tube with a coaxial insert containing 300 μL of 0.197 M TEA in D₂O and 300 μL of the standard in D₂O in the outer compartment. Using integrated peaks corresponding to TEA and the sample, the concentration of product **1** in the solution was determined first using Equation 6.4 to convert the TEA peak intensity from inside to outside the coaxial insert followed by Equation 6.5 to get the concentration of product **1**, where the normalized intensity for the sample (corrected for the number of equivalent protons) equals the measured intensity, $I_{sample} = I_{sample}$, because there is only one proton associated with product **1**'s peak.

The error associated with this calibration method was found to be 15.4% by using the TEA-ethanolamine system to solve for already known concentrations of TEA and Ethanolamine (Equation 6.3).. Sources for this error include measurement of the concentration of the calibrator as well as variations in the precise volumes of each solution used as such variations are reflected in the integrated signals obtained from the NMR.

6.4.2 Data

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ was used to calibrate the standard, first by using peak intensities in the TEA-ethanolamine system to determine the conversion factor, X , from inside to outside the coaxial insert for the integrated signal intensity produced by 300 μL of TEA (Fig 6.6) and then by obtaining product **1**'s concentration from the peak intensities from a Sample-TEA system (Fig 6.7).

6.4.3 Equations and Calculations Used for Calibration

Finding the Conversion Factor X

$$X = \sqrt{\frac{\text{Ethanolamine}_{out}}{\text{TEA}_{in}} \cdot \frac{\text{TEA}_{out}}{\text{Ethanolamine}_{in}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1.00}{0.43} \cdot \frac{65.80}{1.00}} = 12.37 \quad (6.2)$$

In Equation 6.2, integrated NMR signals are referred to by labels with the molecule name and a subscript denoting location, either inside or outside the coaxial insert

Determining Error in Calibration

$$\left(1 - \frac{[\text{Eth}_{calc}]}{[\text{Eth}_{actual}]}\right) \cdot 100\% = \left(1 - \frac{\frac{[\text{TEA}_{conc}]}{I_{n\text{TEA}}} \cdot I_{n\text{eth}}}{0.197M}\right) \cdot 100\% = \left(1 - \frac{0.197 \cdot \frac{1.00}{0.591 \cdot 2}}{0.197M}\right) \cdot 100\% = 15.4\% \quad (6.3)$$

In Equation 6.3, bracketed items indicate concentrations, with "Eth" used as shorthand for ethanolamine. "In" refers to the normalized integral where both the number of equivalent protons associated with the peak and, in the case of a solution in the coaxial insert, the conversion factor "X" has been accounted for (as demonstrated in Equation 6.4).

FIGURE 6.6: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ s of 0.197 M TEA and 0.197 M ethanolamine were used to determine the conversion factor X from inside to outside the Shegemi tube's coaxial insert using $300\ \mu\text{L}$ for both solutions. In (a), TEA was in the outside compartment with ethanolamine inside the coaxial insert. In (b), TEA is inside the coaxial insert with ethanolamine in the outside compartment. Signal peaks associated with ethanolamine are designated by red arrows, while blue arrows designate TEA's peaks. The TEA peak located at 1.0 ppm and the ethanolamine peak at 3.6 ppm were used for calculating the conversion factor X. The normalized integrations for TEA and ethanolamine, respectively, in (a) are 65.80 and 1.00. In (b), the normalized integrations for TEA and ethanolamine are 0.43 and 1.00, respectively.

FIGURE 6.7: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ of $300\ \mu\text{L}$ of oxazolidinone **1** in a Shegemi tube outside the coaxial insert and $300\ \mu\text{L}$ of $0.197\ \text{M}$ TEA inside the coaxial insert. Marked with red arrows are product **1**'s peaks and marked with blue arrows are TEA's peaks. For calculations, product **1**'s peak at $4.2\ \text{ppm}$ and TEA's peak at $1.0\ \text{ppm}$ were used, with normalized integrations of 1.00 and 0.66 , respectively.

Finding the Standard's Concentration

$$In_{TEA} = \left(\frac{I_{TEA}}{\text{number of protons}} \right) \cdot X = \left(\frac{0.66}{9} \right) \cdot 12.37 = 0.907 \quad (6.4)$$

In Equation 6.4, "In" refers to the normalized integral where both the number of equivalent protons associated with the peak and, in this case because the TEA solution was in the coaxial insert, the conversion factor "X" has been taken into account.

$$[Sample_{conc}] = \left(\frac{[TEA_{conc}]}{In_{TEA}} \right) \cdot In_{sample} = \left(\frac{0.197\ \text{M}}{0.907} \right) \cdot 1.00 = 0.2167\ \text{M} \quad (6.5)$$

In Equation 6.5, bracketed items indicate concentrations, and "In" refers to the normalized integral where both the number of equivalent protons associated with the peak and, in this case of the TEA solution because it was in the coaxial insert, the conversion factor "X" has been taken into account. $In_{sample} = I_{sample}$, because there is only one proton associated with product **1**'s peak.

6.4.4 Analysis and Discussion

The calibration method allows us to measure the concentration of product **1** in the sample with only a 15.4% error. Any error due to this calibration technique would be systematic and impact all following results equally, which is acceptable for this project because such an error would just affect the quantum yield curve by a constant factor, which will not alter comparisons between wavelengths or the shape of the quantum yield curve. Because this calibration method carries a 15.4% error on the measured 0.2167 M concentration, we can observe that $0.2167 - 0.2167 \cdot 0.154 = 0.1842$ M and $0.2167 + 0.2167 \cdot 0.154 = 0.2492$ M. Therefore it is fairly safe to proceed with a rounded value of 0.2 M for the concentration of product **1**. This calibrated sample can confidently be used as a standard in the next stages of method development, namely for development of the methods for LC-MS detection and sample preparation by extraction.

6.5 Developing a LC-MS Detection Method

The next stage in development was to obtain a detection method. Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS) works by combining the capability of liquid chromatography (LC) to separate molecules based on physical properties (like size or polarity) with the analytical capability of mass spectrometry (MS).

Liquid chromatography consists of a solid phase (called the 'column') and a mobile phase that 'pushes' the compounds through the column. Different combinations of solid and mobile phases will optimize the retention of different molecules, meaning the amount of time molecules take to pass through the column, allowing for a desired molecule to be separated out of a crude mixture. As the molecules exit the LC component of the device they enter the MS, which determines a molecule's mass to charge ratio allowing for compound identification via determination of its exact mass. MS can also be used quantitatively, as the signal strength is representative of the abundance of material. LC-MS has numerous advantages, the first being its high sensitivity, able to make detections on the order of a hundred pmoles. Because molecules are separated by the column, LC-MS can be used to make quantitative measurements in crude mixtures without the need for extensive purification; furthermore, the combination of LC with MS allows simultaneous analysis of multiple molecules in a sample. Drawbacks for LC-MS include difficulties with optimizing the solid and mobile phase for small or highly polar molecules, and some molecules can fall apart or degrade while passing through the column, making quantitation less accurate. In order to be certain that LC-MS can be used quantitatively, it is necessary to determine a solid and mobile phase that provide a few minutes of retention on the column (in order to separate the target molecule from the mixture) and to ensure a linear relationship between detected signal and concentration, i.e. the calibration curve must be linear (Fig 6.8). Even though an optimized method for using LC-MS to detect oxazolidinone **1** was developed successfully for this project, it was fairly difficult to develop this method because the target molecule is both polar and fairly small, with a molecular weight of 103.8 amu (generally weights above 100 amu are preferred). However, because **1** was shown to be stable under the conditions in the column and a linear response was observed between concentration and detected signal, quantitation can be achieved using a system employing acidic conditions on a Hilic column (Agilent 2.1x100

mm Zorbax Hilic Plus, 3.5 μm particle size) with 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid in water-ACN using an isocratic method with 90% ACN (See Appendix A for a more detailed methodology).

6.5.1 LC-MS Methods Tested

Using the standard obtained with the procedure detailed in Section 6.1, multiple solid and mobile phase combinations for the LC were tested for retention of product **1** on an Agilent LC-MS equipped with an MS Q-TOF (Model G6520A) featuring an Electrospray Ionization Source with a lower detection limit of 100-200 pmol. (Complete specifications for the instrument are included in Appendix A)

TABLE 6.1: **Tested Stationary and Mobile Phase Combinations**

Stationary Phase	Mobile Phase	Retention
C18	Water-ACN	No
C18	Water-ACN with 0.1% Formic Acid	No
PFP	Water-ACN with 0.1% Formic Acid	No
PFP	100% Water	Yes
Hilic	Water-ACN	No
Hilic	1 mM Ammonium Formate in Water-ACN	No
Hilic	10 mM Ammonium Formate in Water-ACN	Yes

The tested solid phases included silica linked-octadecyl carbon chain (C18) columns, pentafluorophenyl (PFP) columns, and hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (Hilic) columns. Tested mobile phases included combinations of water, ACN, formic acid, and ammonium formate. The only solid phases providing retention of oxazolidinone **1** were the PFP column and the Hilic column (Table 6.1), with the most retention observed with a Hilic column solid phase while

using a mobile phase consisting of 10 mM ammonium formate in water-ACN. The PFP column with 100% water worked reasonably well, but the Hilic column provided a superior linear response between detected signal and concentration (Fig 6.8).

6.5.2 LC-MS Calibration Curve

A LC-MS detection method using a Hilic column solid phase (Agilent 2.1x100 mm Zorbax Hilic Plus, 3.5 μm particle size) and a 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid in water-ACN mobile phase provided approximately a 3.5 minute retention time, and a linear relationship between detection signal and concentration was observed, as demonstrated by the linear calibration curve (Fig 6.8). The calibration curve was obtained by analyzing several samples of known concentrations on the LC-MS and plotting concentrations against detected signal intensity. Because the calibration curve is linear, quantitation is possible through a reliable conversion between signal intensity and product concentration.

FIGURE 6.8: The LC-MS calibration curve obtained for oxazolidinone **1** when using acidic conditions on a Hilic column using 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid in water-ACN using an isocratic method with 90% ACN. The linear fit demonstrates a consistent relationship between detection signal and concentration. This curve can be used to convert signal intensity recorded by the LC-MS to a quantified concentration.

6.5.3 MS-MS of Oxazolidinone **1**

When using LC-MS, it is valuable to examine the molecule's fragmentation pattern to make sure that the examined compound is indeed the desired target, as the detected fragments should be identifiable with pieces of the target molecule. If the fragmentation pattern produces signals that cannot be matched to parts of the target molecule, then it is possible that another species with the same

mass is actually being detected. In essence, the fragmentation can provide information about the molecule's structure, allowing for distinction between molecules with the same mass that may differ in structural arrangement.

A mass spectrometry-mass spectrometry (MS-MS) experiment can be used to obtain a molecule's fragmentation pattern. The technique first uses mass spectrometry to isolate molecules with a desired weight before passing them through a beam of nitrogen particles, which induce fragmentation. The fragments are then analyzed by mass spectrometry, providing the abundance and exact mass of each fragment. For oxazolidinone **1**, the predicted fragmentation would be the oxazolidinone ring decomposes to its constituent glycolaldehyde and cyanate components. Because analysis with the mass spectrometer is conducted in positive mode, detection of the oxazolidinone and glycolaldehyde should occur, while the negatively charged cyanate should be absent. In Figure 6.9, it is observed that the fragmentation pattern of the molecule with a weight of 104 amu includes peaks at both 104 amu and 60 amu, corresponding to oxazolidinone **1** and glycolaldehyde, respectively, and confirming that the detected molecule is indeed product **1**.

FIGURE 6.9: In this figure, the 104 peak associated with the oxazolidinone and a 60 peak corresponding to the glycolaldehyde fragment of the oxazolidinone ring are present. Cyanate is not detected because it is a negative ion and the MS-MS was used in positive mode. The identification of the oxazolidinone and glycolaldehyde peaks reinforce the identity of the product as oxazolidinone **1**.

6.5.4 Analysis and Discussion

By developing an LC-MS method exhibiting retention of product **1** and a linear relationship between detected signal and concentration, it is possible to measure the abundance of oxazolidinone **1** in a sample, which can be converted into a quantified concentration using a calibration curve (Fig 6.8) obtained using a standard of known concentration. Further, MS-MS (Fig 6.9) confirms that the detected molecule at 104 amu is indeed oxazolidinone **1**, as the fragmentation pattern includes the predictable masses of both the oxazolidinone and its glycolaldehyde

component. With a reliable detection method developed, the next step in developing the analytics for the project is to obtain a consistently uniform method of sample preparation for the LC-MS. By using a standard of known concentration and the developed LC-MS method, it will be possible to test how much product is retained during preparation (efficiency) and how consistently processing can be applied.

6.6 Efficiency of Sample Preparation

In order to use LC-MS to detect the abundance of **1** in samples collected from UV reactions, it is necessary to use a consistent method of sample preparation. The samples must be processed because the crude reaction mixture contains particulate by-products as well as salts (mostly cyanide and the copper complex) that could harm the LC-MS by precipitating in the tubing during solvent changes. Additionally, by cleaning up the sample and removing contaminants, signal to noise can be improved.

Because samples must be prepared, it is critical that processing occur uniformly, as variations in sample preparation can mask the influence of changes in UV irradiation. The method described in this section successfully prepares samples uniformly for detection of product **1** by LC-MS, employing organic extraction on a 96-well plate to ensure uniform treatment of all samples. The extraction procedure has a measured efficiency of 4% (Table 6.2), indicating that 4% of the total compound is retained through the process. This low efficiency is not of concern because LC-MS is so sensitive that the samples will still need to be diluted 100x following the extraction. With the development of the sample preparation method, the analytics required for obtaining time-courses of UV reactions are now complete.

6.6.1 Methods

To prepare samples for processing by the LC-MS, first 10 μL of each sample (aqueous) was added to a well in a glass-coated 96-well plate before being diluted with an addition 40 μL of LC-grade H_2O . 150 μL of the organic phase, consisting of a 4:1 mixture of chloroform to isopropanol was added to each sample, and samples were mixed 10x using a Hamilton syringe. The 96-well plate was then centrifuged for 5 minutes at 3000 rpm to separate the organic and aqueous layers. A Hamilton syringe was then used to transfer 50 μL of the organic layer to a new well. After all samples were dried, 50 μL of LC-grade ACN was added to each well. The samples, now dissolved in ACN, were transferred to Agilent LC-MS glass vials equipped with deactivated glass inserts equipped with polymer feet. Samples are diluted another 100x for processing by LC-MS.

To determine the extraction efficiency, 500 μM samples of **1** were prepared from a calibrated solution to undergo processing and serve as controls. 4 samples were processed by extraction and their LC-MS detection signals were compared to the average detection signal of the 3 controls to get the efficiency of sample preparation (Table 6.2).

6.6.2 Data

The efficiency of 4% for the sample preparation by extraction was determined with LC-MS by comparing the intensities detected by LC-MS of 4 processed samples with the average detection of 3 controls.

TABLE 6.2: **Efficiency of Extraction Method for Sample Preparation**

Control Sample Number	Signal Detection	Extracted Sample Number	Signal Detection	Efficiency
1	1636529	1	64030	3.87%
2	1637309	2	62089	3.76%
3	1684958	3	73634	4.45%
		4	64894	3.93%
Average	1652932	Average	66161.75	4.03%
Standard Deviation	27738.07 2%	Standard Deviation	5117.73 8%	0.37%

6.6.3 Analysis and Discussion

With a complete system for processing samples and quantifying the amount of product **1**, it is now possible to perform analytical studies of the pathway proposed by Ritson and Sutherland in 2012³. LC-MS enables both quantification and identification of product **1**, and uniform sample preparation via t extraction in a glass 96-well plate ensures that measurements are quantitative. Because **1** is polar, it has a greater affinity for the aqueous phase than the organic phase, and so the extraction efficiency is low, only 4%, as most of the molecule remains in the water layer. While the 4% extraction efficiency may seem low, it is actually acceptable because of the high sensitivity of LC-MS. While these methods are tuned to optimize detection of product **1**, similar methods can certainly be applied to other molecules; however, the details of the LC-MS method and sample preparation would need to be adjusted to fit the properties of such other compounds if they were to be examined. For larger molecules like ribonucleotides developing such

methods would be far easier than the small and polar oxazolidinone **1** examined in this study.

Chapter 7

Determining the Photon Flux

As the goal of this project is to enable construction of quantum yield curves describing reactivity as a function of wavelength, it is necessary to obtain the incident photon flux provided by the UV source at each wavelength tested. The quantum yield is determined by dividing the reaction rate by the number of incident photons, which when measured for isolated wavelengths provides points on the quantum yield curve.

In order to obtain the incident photon flux, a photometer can be used to obtain a power reading, which can then be converted to photon flux. The photometer used in this study detects photons via a thermal sensor which converts a thermal reading into power. Because the thermal sensor exhibits wavelength independence in the UV, these power readings can then be converted directly into photon fluxes utilizing the equation for the energy of a photon (Equation 7.1). Because only part of the solution is under irradiation at a given time, it is also necessary to find the average flux experienced by the reaction mixture as a whole (Equation 7.2).

In constructing the quantum yield curve for the Ritson Process, it is desired to distinguish between the 254 nm irradiation provided by the Rayonet photochemical reactor used in the Sutherland group's original experiment³ and the 265 nm excitation predicted by Banerjee *et al.*¹⁵. Sufficient resolution will be provided by a bandwidth of 5 nm, and for the wavelength dependent trials it seems reasonable to use increments of 5 nm in order to generate the quantum yield curve. Consequently, the incident photon flux was determined for the 75 W Tunable PowerArc with a bandwidth of 5 nm at each 5 nm increment in the UV.

7.1 Methods and Calculations

Obtaining Power Readings with Photometer

A Thorlabs High Sensitivity Thermal Sensor (S401C) equipped with a PM100USB Power and Energy Meter Interface was used to obtain the power provided by the 75 W Tunable Power Arc set at a bandwidth of 5 nm for wavelengths between 200 nm and 300 nm at increments of 5 nm. Power (μW) as a function of wavelength (nm) is provided in Figure 7.1.

Calculating Incident Photons

Under the assumptions that only a small fraction of light is absorbed and that absorption is linear in intensity (i.e. no saturation of the photochemistry has occurred), the incidence of photons was calculated for each wavelength using Equation 7.1.

$$\text{Photons}/s = (\text{Power}) \cdot \frac{\lambda}{h \cdot c} \quad (7.1)$$

Calculating Average Photon Flux Over Whole Volume

Because the reaction mixture is stirred in order to expose the entire sample to irradiation, at a given time only a fraction of the solution is irradiated at a given

time. This must be accounted for in the calculation of incident photon flux, as the average intensity experienced by the solution as a whole will be lower than the incident flux provided by the irradiation beam. To make this correction, the beam is approximated by a 2 mm by 2 mm square profile (providing an irradiation area of 0.04 cm^2), passing through the cuvette's pathlength of 1 cm. This means that $40 \mu\text{L}$ are being irradiated out of a total reaction volume of $800 \mu\text{L}$ contained in the cuvette (a MicroQuartz Stirring Cell, 28-Q-10-MS, manufactured by Starna Cells, Inc.); therefore, the average incident photon flux can be calculated using Equation 7.2. It can be noted that the arbitrary approximation of the beam profile is accounted for in the irradiation volume, and consequently any beam profile can be chosen and still deliver the same answer (i.e. if instead it had been assumed that the beam profile was 0.8 cm^2 and the entire $800 \mu\text{L}$ was irradiated, the correction would still be to divide the Photons/s by 0.5 cm^2).

$$\text{Photons/s/cm}^2 = \frac{(\text{Photons/s})}{(\text{BeamArea}) \cdot \frac{\text{TotalVolume}}{\text{IrradiatedVolume}}} = \frac{(\text{Photons/s})}{(0.04\text{cm}^2) \cdot \frac{800\mu\text{L}}{40\mu\text{L}}} = \frac{(\text{Photons/s})}{0.8\text{cm}^2} \quad (7.2)$$

7.2 Data

Using a 5 nm bandwidth, the power delivered by the 75 W Tunable Power Arc at wavelengths between 200 nm and 300 nm was measured and displayed in Figure 7.1. These power readings were then converted to incident photon fluxes, shown in figure 7.2, making the correction to average over the entire reaction volume as only part of the mixture is irradiated at a given time.

FIGURE 7.1: The power output of the 75 W Tunable Power Arc set at a 5 nm bandwidth was measured using a high sensitivity thermal sensor. As seen in the Tunable PowerArc's spectrum in Chapter 3, the power diminishes as the wavelength decreases.

FIGURE 7.2: The incident photon flux was calculated from the power readings displayed in Figure 7.1, using Equation 7.1 to obtain the number of incident photons and Equation 7.2 to account for the irradiation volume. It can be observed that the flux diminishes with decreasing wavelength. Note that the y axis is scaled by 10^{11}

7.3 Analysis and Discussion

By examining the incident photon flux provided by the 75 W Tunable PowerArc (Fig 7.2), it becomes apparent that the number of photons supplied by the lamp diminishes with decreasing wavelength. As the number of incident photons is not uniform across wavelengths, it is necessary to take into account the incident photon flux in order to compare the wavelength sensitivity of UV reactions. In generating the quantum yield curve, reaction rate at a given wavelength is divided by the incident photon flux, thereby providing a measure of reactivity on a per photon basis and enabling evaluation of UV sensitivity. Obtaining the incident photon flux provided by the Tunable Lamp was the final piece in the development of this method for evaluating the wavelength sensitivity of UV reactions, and now it will be possible to use the entire method to evaluate the feasibility of reactions, including the Ritson Process.

Chapter 8

Next Steps and Applications

8.1 A Complete Method For Measuring the Wavelength Dependence of Reactions

This project has successfully developed a method for measuring the wavelength sensitivity of UV-driven photochemical reactions, allowing for a bridge between results in the chemical laboratory and the prebiotic environment. By using the 75 W Tunable PowerArc to isolate wavelengths, it is possible to examine the wavelength dependence of the reaction rate. In order to measure reaction rate, detection of product **1** in samples taken at various time-points can be achieved using a LC-MS detection method employing a Hilic column and a 10 mM ammonium formate and 0.1% formic acid in water-ACN mobile phase (See Appendix A for a complete methodology for the LC-MS). In order to use LC-MS as the detection method, the extraction method detailed in Section 6.6 can be used to process the samples and remove contaminants including salts like cyanide. By dividing the reaction rates at isolated wavelengths by the incident photon flux, quantum

yields are determined, providing points on the quantum yield curve, providing the number of molecules reacting per number of incident photons. By dividing this curve by the absorption spectrum (the number of molecules excited per number of incident photons) of the copper(I) cyanide complex, the quantum efficiency curve can be obtained, providing the number of molecules reacting per number of excited molecules. The quantum yield and quantum efficiency curves then provide a detailed probe into the reaction's ultraviolet dependence, allowing for evaluation as a robust reaction able to proceed under many ultraviolet environments or a sensitive one dependent on only a narrow range of wavelengths.

8.2 Next Steps

Now that this project has developed a method for measuring the ultraviolet sensitivity of photochemical reactions, there are several directions for the project to progress beyond the completion of this thesis. These steps will be pursued by the author in the next several months and through the end of the upcoming summer.

The first step after the completion of this thesis is to apply the entire method to the Ritson Process. By measuring the quantum yield and quantum efficiency curves, it will be possible to evaluate whether the reaction is robust or sensitive to the ultraviolet environment. Should it be robust and viable under irradiation by many UV wavelengths, then the reaction is likely feasible under a variety of UV environments, including the prebiotic Earth and potentially habitable exoplanets. In the case that it is sensitive, only viable under a narrow set of wavelengths, then it will be important to consider factors that might absorb at those wavelengths, like atmospheric absorption, when considering the reaction's feasibility. Additionally, the quantum yield curve will allow for determination of

whether the reaction proceeds in a photoredox cycle, as suggested by Sutherland's group³, or at a specific electronic excitation, as suggested by Banerjee *et al.*¹⁵. In the case that Sutherland is correct, one would expect a curve exhibiting activity below some wavelength corresponding to a cut-off threshold for the ejection of the solvated electron, and the quantum yield curve would follow the absorption activity of the copper(I) cyanide complex (as photon absorption would dominate reactivity). In the case that a specific electronic transition is required, one would expect a more efficient use of photons at a specific wavelength, corresponding to the specific transition, predicted to be at 265 nm by Banerjee *et al.*¹⁵.

Additionally, the method developed in this thesis can be applied to the UV-driven steps in the prebiotic synthesis of RNA proposed by Powner *et al.*, in particular, to explore the reported result that the biologic RNA monomers were enriched relative to alternative structures when using a 254 nm Hg arc lamp². This suggests that the biologic RNA monomers are more stable at 254 nm, and should this hold across UV wavelengths, then a strong argument could be made for UV as the source of selection for the RNA structures critical to biology. Consequently, it will be incredibly insightful to apply the method developed in this thesis to examine the stability and degradation of RNA monomers and competing alternative structures. Essentially, the quantum yield curves for the degradation of each molecule will enable comparisons across wavelengths and determine if UV was indeed a selection force favoring the RNA monomers later adopted by biology. On the other hand, it would also be an interesting discovery if different UV wavelengths should prove to select for different sets of monomers.

8.3 Applications

Determining the wavelength dependence of photochemical reactions has several critical applications pertaining to investigations of the origins of life. Firstly, in some cases the shape of quantum yield curves can allow for elucidation of the UV-mechanism propelling a reaction pathway, such as distinguishing between the photoredox cycle³ and specific electronic excitation¹⁵ proposed for the Ritson Process. Additionally, by determining the wavelength dependence of UV-driven steps in proposed syntheses of key precursors to biologic molecules like RNA or amino acids, it will be possible to evaluate their feasibility under the UV conditions present on the prebiotic Earth, as the UV environment can be determined using astrophysical modeling^{9,29,30}. Essentially, this means that astrophysical models can now be used to constrain UV-dependent prebiotic chemistry. Finally, reactions deemed critical to the development of life as we know it on Earth, such as reactions leading to key molecules like RNA, can be used to constrain the search for habitable, life-bearing exoplanets. By determining the UV conditions necessary for these critical reactions, it will be possible to constrain what types of planets could host such chemistry. Such information could then be used to inform the allocation of observational resources for attempted detection of biomarkers, like oxygen in the atmosphere, making the search for life in the galaxy more efficient by ruling out planets unable to host the chemistry required for life as we know it.

Appendix A

LCMS Acquisition Method

The following pages include the acquisition method employed to acquire all of the LC-MS data used in this report. These pages were obtained directly from the device, and they detail the model numbers of each component as well as the parameters used during injections.

Acquisition Method Report

Agilent Technologies

Acquisition Method Info

Method Name HILIC with Ammonium formate oxazolidinone v11 no bottom sensing.m
Method Path C:\MassHunter\Methods\Dimitar\HILIC with Ammonium formate oxazolidinone v11 no bottom sensing.m
Method Description Default Method

Device List

HiP Sampler
 Binary Pump
 Column Comp.
 DAD
 Q-TOF

TOF/Q-TOF Mass Spectrometer

Component Name	MS Q-TOF	Component Model	G6520A
Ion Source	Dual ESI	Stop Time (min)	No Limit/As Pump
Can wait for temp.	Enable	Fast Polarity	N/A
MS Abs. threshold	200	MS Rel. threshold(%)	0.010
MS/MS Abs. threshold	5	MS/MS Rel. threshold(%)	0.010
Tune File	AutoTune.tun		

Time Segments

Time Segment #	Start Time (min)	Diverter Valve State	Storage Mode	Ion Mode
1	0	MS	Profile	Dual ESI
2	1.5	MS	Profile	Dual ESI
3	4	Waste	None	Dual ESI

Time Segment 1

Acquisition Mode MS1

Min Range (m/z)	50
Max Range (m/z)	1000
Scan Rate (spectra/sec)	1.50

Source Parameters

Parameter	Value
Gas Temp (°C)	300
Gas Flow (l/min)	10
Nebulizer (psig)	30

Scan Segments

Scan Seg #	Ion Polarity	Collision Energy
1	Positive	0

Scan Segment 1

Scan Source Parameters

Parameter	Value
VCap	4000
Fragmentor	160
Skimmer1	60
OctopoleRFPeak	650

Acquisition Method Report

Agilent Technologies

Time Segment 2

Acquisition Mode MS1

Min Range (m/z)	50
Max Range (m/z)	1000
Scan Rate (spectra/sec)	1.50

Source Parameters

Parameter	Value
Gas Temp (°C)	300
Gas Flow (l/min)	10
Nebulizer (psig)	30

Scan Segments

Scan Seg #	Ion Polarity	Collision Energy
1	Positive	0

Scan Segment 1

Scan Source Parameters

Parameter	Value
VCap	4000
Fragmentor	160
Skimmer1	60
OctopoleRFPeak	650

Time Segment 3

Acquisition Mode MS1

Min Range (m/z)	50
Max Range (m/z)	1000
Scan Rate (spectra/sec)	1.50

Source Parameters

Parameter	Value
Gas Temp (°C)	300
Gas Flow (l/min)	10
Nebulizer (psig)	30

Scan Segments

Scan Seg #	Ion Polarity	Collision Energy
1	Positive	0

Scan Segment 1

Scan Source Parameters

Parameter	Value
VCap	4000
Fragmentor	160
Skimmer1	60
OctopoleRFPeak	650

ReferenceMasses

Ref Mass Enabled	Enabled
Use Bottle A RefNebulizer	True
Ref Nebulizer (psig)	2

AutoRecalibration

Average Scans	1
Detection Window (ppm)	100
Min Height (counts)	1000

Reference Masses

<Positive>
121.05087300
922.00979800

Chromatograms

Chrom Type	Label	Offset	Y-Range
TIC	TIC	15	10000000

Acquisition Method Report

Agilent Technologies

Name: HiP Sampler **Model:** G1367D

Auxiliary

Draw Speed	100.0 µL/min
Eject Speed	100.0 µL/min
Draw Position Offset	7.0 mm
Wait Time After Drawing	2.0 s
Sample Flush Out Factor	5.0
Vial/Well bottom sensing	No

Injection

Injection Mode	Injection with needle wash
Injection Volume	7.50 µL
Needle Wash	
Needle Wash Location	Flush Port
Wash Time	3.0 s

High throughput

Automatic Delay Volume Reduction	No
Overlapped Injection	
Enable Overlapped Injection	No

Valve Switching

Valve Movements	0
Valve Switch Time 1	
Switch Time 1 Enabled	No
Valve Switch Time 2	
Switch Time 2 Enabled	No
Valve Switch Time 3	
Switch Time 3 Enabled	No
Valve Switch Time 4	
Switch Time 4 Enabled	No

Stop Time

Stoptime Mode	As pump/No limit
---------------	------------------

Post Time

Posttime Mode	Off
---------------	-----

Name: Binary Pump **Model:** G1312B

Flow	0.125 mL/min
Use Solvent Types	Yes
Low Pressure Limit	0.00 bar
High Pressure Limit	250.00 bar
Maximum Flow Gradient	100.000 mL/min ²

Stroke A

Automatic Stroke Calculation A	Yes
--------------------------------	-----

Stroke B

Automatic Stroke Calculation B	Yes
--------------------------------	-----

Compress A

Compressibility Mode A	Compressibility Value Set
Compressibility A	50 10e-6/bar

Compress B

Compressibility Mode B	Compressibility Value Set
Compressibility B	115 10e-6/bar

Stop Time

Stoptime Mode	Time set
Stoptime	19.00 min

Post Time

Posttime Mode	Time set
Posttime	4.00 min

Acquisition Method Report

Timetable

Timetable

	Time	Function	Parameter
1	4.00 min	Change Flow	Flow: 0.125 mL/min
2	4.00 min	Change Max. Pressure Limit	Max. Pressure Limit: 250.00 bar
3	4.00 min	Change Solvent Composition	Solvent composition A: 0.0 % B:100.0 %
4	5.00 min	Change Flow	Flow: 0.25 mL/min
5	5.00 min	Change Max. Pressure Limit	Max. Pressure Limit: 250.00 bar
6	5.00 min	Change Solvent Composition	Solvent composition A: 40.0 % B:60.0 %
7	8.00 min	Change Flow	Flow: 0.25 mL/min
8	8.00 min	Change Max. Pressure Limit	Max. Pressure Limit: 250.00 bar
9	8.00 min	Change Solvent Composition	Solvent composition A: 40.0 % B:60.0 %
10	9.00 min	Change Flow	Flow: 0.25 mL/min
11	9.00 min	Change Max. Pressure Limit	Max. Pressure Limit: 250.00 bar
12	9.00 min	Change Solvent Composition	Solvent composition A: 0.0 % B:100.0 %
13	13.00 min	Change Flow	Flow: 0.125 mL/min
14	13.00 min	Change Max. Pressure Limit	Max. Pressure Limit: 250.00 bar
15	13.00 min	Change Solvent Composition	Solvent composition A: 0.0 % B:100.0 %
16	19.00 min	Change Flow	Flow: 0.125 mL/min
17	19.00 min	Change Max. Pressure Limit	Max. Pressure Limit: 250.00 bar
18	19.00 min	Change Solvent Composition	Solvent composition A: 0.0 % B:100.0 %

Solvent Composition

	Channel	Solvent 1	Name 1	Solvent 2	Name 2	Selected	Used	Percent
1	A	H2O	H2O,10mM NH4formate 0.1% FA	H2O	TEA, HFIP, DON NOT USE	Ch. 1	Yes	0.0 %
2	B	ACN	ACN:H2O (9:1) 10mM NH4formate and 0.1% FA	MeOH	MeOH,	Ch. 1	Yes	100.0 %

Name: Column Comp.

Model: G1316B

Valve Position	Port 1 -> 2
Left Temperature Control	
Temperature Control Mode	Not Controlled
Enable Analysis Left Temperature	
Enable Analysis Left Temperature On	Yes
Enable Analysis Left Temperature Value	0.80 °C
Right Temperature Control	
Right temperature Control Mode	Temperature Set
Right temperature	20.00 °C
Enable Analysis Right Temperature	
Enable Analysis Right Temperature On	No
Stop Time	
Stoptime Mode	As pump/injector
Post Time	
Posttime Mode	Off

Acquisition Method Report

Agilent Technologies

Name: DAD

Model: G1315C

Peakwidth	>0.10 min (2.0 s response time) (2.5 Hz)
Slit	4 nm
UV Lamp Required	Yes
Vis Lamp Required	No
Analog Output 1	
Analog 1 Zero Offset	5 %
Analog 1 Attenuation	1000 mAU
Analog Output 2	
Analog 2 Zero Offset	5 %
Analog 2 Attenuation	1000 mAU
Signals	
Prepare Mode	
Margin for negative Absorbance	100 mAU
Autobalance	
Autobalance Prerun	Yes
Autobalance Postrun	No
Spectrum	
Spectrum Range WL from	190 nm
Spectrum Range WL to	400 nm
Spectrum Step	2.0 nm
Spectrum Store	All
Stoptime	
Stoptime Mode	As pump/injector
Posttime	
Posttime Mode	Off

Signals**Signal table**

	Use Sig.	Signal	Wavelength	Bandwidth	Use Ref.	Ref Wavel.	Ref Bandw.
1	Yes	Signal A	214 nm	4 nm	No		
2	Yes	Signal B	280 nm	8 nm	No		
3	Yes	Signal C	203 nm	8 nm	No		
4	Yes	Signal D	214 nm	4 nm	Yes	360 nm	100 nm
5	Yes	Signal E	280 nm	8 nm	Yes	360 nm	100 nm
6	Yes	Signal F	203 nm	8 nm	Yes	360 nm	100 nm
7	No	Signal G					
8	No	Signal H					

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